

UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN

DEPARTMENT OF FOOD SCIENCE

Master Thesis

Meixian Guo

Bioprotective Potential and Inhibitory Mechanisms of Lactic Acid Bacteria against *Bacillus* Species in a Faba Bean-Based Fermentation System

Supervisor: Lene Jespersen

DATE: 01/06/2026

Abstract

With the rapid development of the plant-based foods, their microbial safety issues have attracted increasing attention. *Bacillus* spp. are widely found in plant raw materials and can survive through food processing and storage, leading to product spoilage. This study investigated the inhibitory potential of different lactic acid bacteria strains against *Bacillus subtilis* BxFB-A B1, *Bacillus licheniformis* BxFB-B B2 and *Bacillus subtilis* Natto. The results showed that there were obvious differences in the inhibitory ability of different LAB strains of *Bacillus*, among which the *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* strains showed the strongest antibacterial activity. Supernatant of LAB showed an obvious concentration-dependent inhibitory effect on three *Bacillus* strains, while the antibacterial activity of some *L. plantarum* strains decreased significantly after protease K treatment. The three *Bacillus* strains could maintain growth at pH 5.1, but the growth was significantly inhibited at pH 4.5 and below. Both lactic acid and acetic acid could effectively inhibit the growth of *Bacillus* spp., while the growth of the 40–80 mM treatment group was significantly inhibited. During faba bean fermentation, LAB growth, pH change and organic acid production were monitored at 0, 6, 24, 30, 48 and 72 h. All LAB strains could lead to systemic acidification within 24 hours, while producing organic acids such as lactic acid and acetic acid. *L. plantarum* strain had a strong acid production capacity and accumulated a large amount of lactic acid in the early stage, and in the late stage there was a metabolic change where lactic acid was reducing and acetic acid was increasing. while *L. fermentum* strain showed a more obvious trend of acetic acid accumulation. *L. lactis* strain mainly produced lactic acid in the early stage and then the lactic acid level was maintained at a low level with the increasing production of acetic acid. These results showed that LAB, especially *L. plantarum*, had strong bio-preservation potential in controlling *Bacillus* contamination in plant-based foods.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor, Lene Jespersen, and my co-supervisor, Nadja Larsen, for giving me the opportunity to carry out my master thesis project in the micro section. I truly appreciate their patient guidance, valuable suggestions, and kind support throughout the entire process.

I would also like to thank everyone in the laboratory who helped me during my thesis work. Their assistance and friendly support were very important to me and made my time in the laboratory a memorable experience.

Table of contents

ABSTRACT	2
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	3
1 INTRODUCTION	7
1.1 In general.....	7
1.2 Lactic acid bacteria.....	8
1.2.1 Physiological characteristics of <i>Lactobacillaceae</i>	8
1.2.2 Metabolism of LAB during fermentation.....	8
1.2.3 LAB as bioprotective cultures in food	10
1.2.4 Selection of LAB species	11
1.3 <i>Bacillus</i>.....	12
1.3.1 Physiological characteristics of <i>Bacillus</i>	12
1.3.2 <i>Bacillus</i> as a contaminant in plant-based food systems.....	13
1.3.3 Selection of <i>Bacillus</i> species.....	13
1.4 Limitations of conventional control strategies	14
1.4.1 Limitations of thermal processing in spore inactivation	14
1.4.2 Limitations of chemical and physical preservation methods.....	15
1.4.3 Need for alternative biopreservation strategies	15
1.5 Antimicrobial activity of LAB against <i>Bacillus</i>.....	15
1.5.1 Inhibitory metabolites: The role of organic acids	15
1.5.2 Synergistic interactions between acids and bacteriocins.....	16
1.5.3 Modes of action on vegetative cells and endospores	18
1.5.4 Efficacy and limiting factors in food systems	19

1.6 Faba bean	19
2 MATERIAL AND METHODS	20
2.1 Bacterial strains and growth conditions	20
2.2 Agar spot-lawn assay for screening LAB inhibitory activity	21
2.3 Evaluation of LAB cell-free supernatants against <i>Bacillus</i> spp.....	21
2.4 Well diffusion assay for detection of bacteriocin-like activity	22
2.5 Evaluation of pH tolerance of <i>Bacillus</i> spp.....	22
2.6 Evaluation of organic acid inhibition against <i>Bacillus</i> spp.	22
2.7 Faba bean fermentation with LAB strains	23
2.8 Determination of organic acids by HPLC.....	23
2.9 Data analysis and statistics.....	23
3 RESULTS	24
3.1 Inhibitory activity of LAB strains against <i>Bacillus</i> spp.....	24
3.2 Inhibitory effects of LAB cell-free supernatants against <i>Bacillus</i> spp.	27
3.3 Detection of bacteriocin-like activity.....	30
3.4 pH tolerance of <i>Bacillus</i> spp.	31
3.5 Inhibitory effects of organic acids against <i>Bacillus</i> spp.....	32
3.6 Faba bean fermentation with LAB strains	35
3.6.1 pH changes during faba bean fermentation.....	35
3.6.2 Growth of LAB during faba bean fermentation	37
3.6.3 Organic acid production during faba bean fermentation.....	38
4 DISCUSSION.....	41
4.1 Strain-dependent inhibitory activity of LAB against <i>Bacillus</i> spp.	41
4.2 Role of LAB cell-free supernatants in <i>Bacillus</i> inhibition	43

4.3 Possible contribution of bacteriocin-like antimicrobial compounds	44
4.4 Effects of pH on <i>Bacillus</i> spp. growth	45
4.5 Effects of organic acid on <i>Bacillus</i> spp. growth.....	46
4.6 Faba bean fermentation with LAB strains	48
4.6.1 pH changes and acidification	48
4.6.2 Growth dynamics of LAB strains	49
4.6.3 Organic acid production and acidification	49
5 CONCLUSION.....	54
6 LITERATURE	56
7 APPENDIX.....	66
Appendix 1 - Plate pictures from lawn assay	66
Appendix 2 - Plate pictures from supernatant inhibition	68
Appendix 3 - Plate pictures from pH tolerance of <i>Bacillus</i> spp.....	70
Appendix 4 - Plate pictures from well diffusion assay	71
Appendix 5 - Plate pictures from the organic acids inhibition of <i>Bacillus</i> spp.	73
Appendix 6 - Pictures of fermentation samples.....	74
Appendix 7 - Calibration curves used in fermentation	75

1 Introduction

1.1 In general

The consumption and demand of plant-based foods (PBF) have increased steadily in European countries, due to the environmental benefits and consumers' growing awareness of sustainability (Kyrylenko et al. 2023a). In recent years, plant-based dairy products, plant-based beverages and plant-based meats have been well developed, contributing to improve the environmental conditions. However, this also introduced some new challenges.

Food safety has always been a critical concern. Raw materials of PBF, such as legumes, grains and nuts are easily contaminated by spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms due to their exposure to soil, air and water (Hackl et al. 2013). Moreover, these raw materials typically exhibit high-water activity, neutral pH, and high protein and moisture content, creating the ideal conditions for microbial growth and spoilage (Param Pal Sahota and Hunjan 2017). Therefore, it is crucial to ensure the microbiological safety of PBF.

The conventional industrial methods of microbial control mainly rely on physical treatments, such as high heat, high pressure and radiation processing. Chemical preservatives are also widely used, such as sorbic acid, benzoic acid and their salts. However, the physical treatments can result in nutrient loss, flavour change and high energy cost, whereas the chemical treatments face challenges of clean-label requirements and potential health risks with long-term intake (Cho and Chung 2020a; Mafe et al. 2024). As a result, relying solely on the traditional methods makes it difficult to simultaneously achieve food safety, product quality and meet consumer expectations. Therefore, it is essential to find a green and sustainable antibacterial strategy.

In this context, biopreservation strategy has widely received attention as a sustainable alternative in recent years. The core idea of biopreservation is to use food-grade microorganisms and their metabolites to prevent the growth and activity of pathogens and spoilage microorganisms through mechanisms such as acid production, secretion of antibacterial substances and competitive exclusion (Barcenilla et al. 2022). Compared to traditional approaches, biopreservation is considered more natural and sustainable, particularly suitable for PBF, where clean-label ingredients are highly valued.

Among biopreservation agents, lactic acid bacteria (LAB) has been a common choice due to their strong abilities to produce organic acids and other antimicrobial compounds, which can efficiently inhibit the growth of pathogen and spoilage microorganisms (Gedefa et al. 2025). However, the

inhibitory effect of LAB on *Bacillus* spp. have not been thoroughly investigated. Therefore, this project aimed to evaluate the potential of LAB strains as bioprotective cultures for controlling *Bacillus*.*spp.* and to investigate the underlying mechanisms. Fermentation of faba bean (*Vicia faba*) medium with LAB strains was conducted to simulate the practical plant-based food production.

1.2 Lactic acid bacteria

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are a heterogeneous group of microorganisms. They have been identified as generally regarded as safe (GRAS) and associated with beneficial effects on human health. They exist widely, from the gastrointestinal tracts of humans, animals and insects, through plants and meat, to soil and water (Buron-Moles et al. 2019). They are also found in human milk and the vagina (Chee, Chew, and Than 2020; Riaz Rajoka et al. 2017). LAB have been widely used in food industries, especially in fermented foods such as dairy products (Papagianni 2012).

1.2.1 Physiological characteristics of *Lactobacillaceae*

Lactobacillaceae is the largest and most common family of LAB. They are Gram-positive, catalase-negative, fermentative, facultatively anaerobic, non-spore-forming, rod-shaped or coccobacilli, and produce lactic acid as the major end product of the fermentation. They have complex nutritional requirements for amino acids, peptides, nucleic acid derivatives, vitamins, salts, fatty acids or fatty acid esters and carbohydrates (Mazguene 2023).

1.2.2 Metabolism of LAB during fermentation

LAB can degrade a wide range of carbohydrates during fermentation, from monosaccharides to polysaccharides. The metabolism mainly follows two pathways, homofermentative and heterofermentative, which can be obligate and facultative. The obligate homofermentative species use the Embden–Meyerhof–Parnas (EMP) pathway to degrade only hexose and produce lactic acid as the single end product. Obligate heterofermentative species degrade the hexose by using phosphogluconate pathway, ending up with lactic acid, ethanol, acetic acid or formic acid and carbon dioxide. The facultative heterofermentative species use pentose phosphate pathway (PPP) to metabolize both hexoses and pentoses (García-Cano et al. 2019; König, Unden, and Fröhlich 2017; Kouvari et al. 2020). The metabolic ability of LAB is species-specific or strain specific and depends on their enzymatic profiles (Filannino, Di Cagno, and Gobbetti 2018). The major carbohydrate metabolic pathways and end products in LAB are showed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the fructose and glucose metabolic pathways in LAB and obligate FLAB. Enzymes: ADH, alcohol dehydrogenase; AK, acetate kinase; ALDH, acetaldehyde dehydrogenase; CoA, coenzyme A; EDH, erythritol dehydrogenase; ENO, enolase; E4PPT, erythrose 4-phosphate phosphotransferase; F16DPA, fructose-1,6-diphosphate aldolase; FK, fructokinase; GA3PDH, glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase; G6PDH, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase; LDH, lactate dehydrogenase; MDH, mannitol deshydrogenase; PDH, pyruvate dehydrogenase; 6PFK, 6-phosphofruktokinase; PGDH, 6-phosphogluconate dehydrogenase; G6PI, glucose 6-phosphate isomerase; PGK, phosphoglycerate kinase; PGM, phosphoglyceromutase; PK, pyruvate kinase; PTA, phosphotransacetylase; R5P3E, ribulose-5-phosphate-3-epimerase; TPI, triosephosphate isomerase; and X5PPK, xylulose-5-phosphate phosphoketolase. Adapted from (Mazguene 2023).

LAB also possess a proteolytic system which can degrade protein into necessary peptides and amino acids, contributing to their growth and to beneficial flavour and texture of fermented foods. And the proteolytic system of LAB mainly follows three steps: the action of extracellular enzymes on proteins, transportation of peptides and free amino acids through the cell wall, and lastly, hydrolysis of peptides by intracellular enzymes. However, the enzymes and transporting systems in each step are very strain dependent, resulting in different abilities of LAB to degrade protein (Griffiths and Tellez 2013).

Lipid metabolism is also an important biochemical event during the fermentation by LAB. LAB use esterases (carboxyl ester hydrolases) and lipases (triacylglycerol hydrolases) to cut the ester bonds of triacyl glycerols, release free fatty acids and glycerols, and further synthesize aromatic compounds such as esters and thioesters (Amina et al., 2020). Although the lipid hydrolysis activity of LAB is usually weaker than that of other bacteria, the metabolites are crucial to the sensory properties of fermented food (Deeth 2006).

In addition to the core nutritional metabolism, LAB also show a variety of important auxiliary functions. They can metabolize polyols like glycerol through dehydrogenation or phosphorylation pathway, thus participating in key physiological processes such as phospholipid biosynthesis (Doi and Yuki, 2019). Some strains can synthesize bile saline hydrolase for bile acid metabolism (Prete et al. 2020). In addition, they can not only bio transform and degrade phenolic compounds (Li et al. 2021; Wu et al. 2020) and produce volatile substances (Battelli et al. 2019; Gómez De Cadiñanos et al. 2019), but also can stabilize or eliminate toxins (Luz et al. 2018; Wei et al. 2020), and can remove lead, cadmium (Pakdel et al., 2019), mercury (Jadán-Piedra et al. 2019) through biological adsorption.

1.2.3 LAB as bioprotective cultures in food

LAB, as a biopreservation culture in food, have received wide attention in recent years and are regarded as a natural, sustainable food preservation strategy that conforms to the concept of clean-label. Compared with traditional chemical preservatives or high-strength physical treatment, LAB can not only extend the shelf life of food, but also better maintain the original flavour, texture and nutritional quality of food. Due to the recognized safety status and adaptability, LAB has been widely used in meat products, dairy products, aquatic products and plant-based foods. For example, the application of LAB in cooked ham, smoked salmon, cheese and ready-to-eat vegetables has been shown to effectively inhibit important foodborne pathogens, including *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella* spp. and *Escherichia coli*. (Fischer and Titgemeyer 2023).

1.2.4 Selection of LAB species

Lactiplantibacillus plantarum

Lactiplantibacillus plantarum is a species within the genus *Lactiplantibacillus* and is a Gram-positive bacterium. The cells are rod-shaped and occur singly, in pairs, or in chains. They are widely found in human body and fermented foods like sauerkraut, leek, radish roots, fermented sausages, fermented milk, cheeses and sourdough. It has also been found in plant raw materials, such as olives and cucumbers. *L. plantarum* has a dominant position in the foods above due to its large metabolic capacities and their ability to tolerate acidic conditions. Moreover, some *L. plantarum* strains have the ability to produce bioactive compounds such as γ -aminobutyric acid, vitamins, such as riboflavin and folate, bioactive peptides and enzymes that increase the nutritional value of fermented food, such as phytase, and degrade biogenic amines, making them an attractive option for utilization as starter cultures (Paramithiotis 2025).

In addition, *L. plantarum* could interfere with the virulence mechanisms of an extended range of foodborne pathogens. There has been a study showing that *L. plantarum* could increase the levels of expression of the mRNA of some mucins, inhibiting the cell attachment of enteropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (Quinto et al. 2014).

Limosilactobacillus fermentum

Limosilactobacillus fermentum is also a species within the genus *Limosilactobacillus* and is a Gram-positive heterofermentative bacterium. They can be found in milk products, sewage, manure, fermenting vegetables and the mouth and feces of humans. *L. fermentum* has been identified as a safe probiotic (Zhao et al. 2019). Studies have shown that the bacterium can survive in the gastrointestinal environment, adhere to the intestinal mucosa, and inhibit a variety of pathogens, including *Staphylococcus aureus* (Kang et al. 2017), *Helicobacter pylori* (García et al. 2017), *Candida albicans* (Rossoni et al. 2018) and *Campylobacter jejuni* (Lehri et al. 2017).

In addition, *L. fermentum* has also been reported to possess immunomodulatory properties. Cell models, animal experiments and clinical trial studies showed that some specific *L. fermentum* strains could regulate inflammatory response and regulate congenital and adaptive immunity. These effects include regulating the production of cytokines (Barone et al. 2016) and alleviating inflammatory diseases such as colitis (Cui et al. 2016) and respiratory infections (García et al. 2017).

Lactococcus lactis

Lactococcus lactis is classified as a gram-positive, spherical, homofermentative, non-sporulating, and facultative anaerobic gut bacteria. It has been generally recognized as safe (GRAS) status and has been widely used in food fermentation due to its technological properties, including extracellular secretion capacity, surface display systems, and the availability of various cloning and inducible expression vectors. *L. lactis* has been long applied in cheese, yoghurt and sauerkraut (Song et al. 2017a). In addition to enhancing flavour, some strains can also produce bacteriocins which can help with food preservation (De Arauz et al. 2009).

In addition, *L. lactis* has also become the model LAB for genetic engineering due to its small-sized fully sequenced genome, and the development of successfully compatible genetic engineering tools such as cloning and expression systems with customizable options (Song et al. 2017b).

1.3 *Bacillus*

1.3.1 Physiological characteristics of *Bacillus*

Bacillus is a genus of Gram-positive and rod-shaped, which are widely found in soil, plants and food processing environments. One of the most important physiological characteristics of *Bacillus* is that *Bacillus* can form highly tolerant spores. Previous studies have pointed out that spores are resistant to heat, radiation, chemicals and extreme pH conditions, making them more difficult to inactivate than vegetative cells. The tolerance of spores is related to its special structure, including thick spore coat, low water content and high concentrations of dipicolinic acid (DPA) and divalent cations in the core. In addition, *Bacillus* spores are formed under limited nutritional conditions, and when the environment provides amino acids, sugars and other nutrients, they can germinate and resume growth quickly (Cho and Chung 2020b).

In addition, *Bacillus* also has a strong ability to secrete extracellular enzymes, such as amylase, protease and cellulase. Some strains can also produce antibacterial peptides and bacteriocins, which have an inhibitory effect on pathogenic bacteria. And due to strong tolerance, metabolic activity and intestinal adaptability, some *Bacillus* strains have been developed into probiotics and food fermentation strains (Elshaghabe et al. 2017).

1.3.2 *Bacillus* as a contaminant in plant-based food systems

With the rapid development of PBF, especially plant based milk substitutes, their microbial safety has gradually attracted consumers' attention. Kyrylenko et al. (2023b) have pointed out that *Bacillus* is widely found in soil and plant environments, thus plant raw materials are naturally and easily contaminated. These spores-forming bacteria are able to form heat-resistant endospores which can survive after pasteurization or strong heat treatment, and may germinate and grow again during subsequent storage, leading to food deterioration, such as bitterness, sourness, odor, precipitation or texture degradation, and fat decomposition. The study analysed a variety of raw materials used in plant-based dairy products, such as pea, faba bean, oat, rice and almond. The results showed that the number of spores accounted for a high proportion of the total bacterial count, especially in pea isolates, faba bean isolates and oat products. Among them, *Bacillus licheniformis* and the *Bacillus. cereus* group were the most detected *Bacillus* species in pea and oat raw materials.

1.3.3 Selection of *Bacillus* species

Bacillus subtilis

Bacillus subtilis is a Gram-positive, rod-shaped, aerobic bacterium, existing in the plant surface and the rhizosphere. *B. subtilis* is also one of the most deeply studied Gram-positive model bacteria at present, with fast growth rate and easy to cultivate. Under suitable conditions, the multiplication time can be as short as about 20 min, so *B. subtilis* is often widely used in basic microbiology research and industrial production.

One of the most important characteristics of *B. subtilis* is the ability to form endospores. When the environment is undernourished or coerced, *B. subtilis* can form a highly tolerant spore structure through complex cell differentiation processes. Spores can remain dormant for a long time and re-germinate into trophic cells after the environment is restored to suitability. *B. subtilis* can produce a variety of extracellular enzymes and metabolites, act as a plant promoter and grow rapidly in a food system rich in protein and starch. The bacterium can also secrete a large number of proteases and amylases. Therefore, *B. subtilis* is widely used in the production of enzyme preparations in industry.

It is worth noting that *B. subtilis* is also closely related to food fermentation. It is specifically mentioned in the literature that it is the core strain of natto, a traditional Japanese fermented food. However, in other plant-based food systems, some *Bacillus* strains may also become potential

spoilage bacteria due to their acid resistance, spore formation ability and protein hydrolysis activity; therefore, they are often used as target bacteria in bioprotective studies (Errington and Aart 2020).

Bacillus licheniformis

Bacillus licheniformis is a Gram-positive and rod-shaped bacteria, which is widely distributed in soil, water and food processing environments. *B. licheniformis* is one of the important industrial microorganisms in the *Bacillus* genus. *B. licheniformis* can also form highly tolerant spores with strong resistance to high temperature, dryness and a variety of adverse environments (He et al. 2023).

B. licheniformis has been listed by the FDA as one of the GRAS strains, which can be used for food fermentation and functional food development. In traditional fermented foods, *B. licheniformis* often participates in the fermentation of soybeans, such as the fermentation process of Korean traditional food chungkookjang. In addition, *B. licheniformis* can also produce a variety of extracellular enzymes, including protease, amylase and lipase. Therefore, it is also widely used in food processing and industrial biological manufacturing (Raman et al. 2025).

However, *B. licheniformis* is also an important spoilage bacterium due to the ability to produce protease and amylase. And because of its strong tolerance, it is difficult to completely remove this bacterium in food processing. In the dairy industry, *B. licheniformis* will degrade the nutrients in milk, resulting in a decrease in product quality and a shorter shelf life. A previous study also reported that the spoilage rate associated with *B. licheniformis* in raw milk ranged from 6.8% to 47.4%, and this species has frequently been detected in dairy processing equipment and end products like UHT milk and milk powder (Kim and Son 2025).

1.4 Limitations of conventional control strategies

1.4.1 Limitations of thermal processing in spore inactivation

Heat treatment is one of the most used methods for controlling microbial contaminants in the food industry. Technologies such as pasteurization and ultra-high temperature treatment are widely used. However, the spores which *Bacillus* forms are extremely tolerant, making it difficult to achieve complete inactivation (Cho and Chung 2020b). Therefore, under conventional pasteurization conditions, spores can often survive and re-germinate into vegetative cells under suitable conditions, which leads to subsequent food contamination or safety problems (Dash et al. 2022).

1.4.2 Limitations of chemical and physical preservation methods

In addition to heat treatment, a variety of chemical and physical preservation methods are also widely used in the food industry to inhibit the growth of microorganisms, such as adding preservatives, reducing water activity and adjusting pH. These methods can slow down the reproduction of microorganisms to a certain extent and improve the safety and shelf life of food (Mafe et al. 2024).

However, for *Bacillus*, these traditional preservation methods still have obvious limitations. First, the spore structure of *Bacillus* has a strong tolerance to a variety of chemical preservatives. In addition, in plant-based food system, high protein and carbohydrate content may buffer or protect some antibacterial agents, thus reducing their antibacterial effect. On the other hand, physical methods such as reducing water activity or changing processing conditions are able to inhibit the growth of some microorganisms, but they are often insufficient to completely prevent the survival and subsequent germination of spores. Moreover, these methods may have an adverse impact on the quality, taste and nutritional characteristics of food (Mafe et al. 2024, Soni et al. 2016).

1.4.3 Need for alternative biopreservation strategies

Based on this background, the development of safe, efficient and sustainable alternative strategies has become an important research direction. And biopreservation methods based on natural microorganisms and their metabolites have attracted increasing attention because of their effective antibacterial activity and minimal impact on food quality (Barcenilla et al. 2022).

LAB are considered a promising bioprotective strategy for controlling *Bacillus* contamination because of their ability to produce various antibacterial substances such as organic acids and bacteriocins, as well as their good adaptability in the food system (Gedefa et al. 2025). Therefore, a systematic study of the inhibitory effect of LAB against *Bacillus* spp. and the underlying mechanism is important to the development of novel biological preservation strategies.

1.5 Antimicrobial activity of LAB against *Bacillus*

1.5.1 Inhibitory metabolites: The role of organic acids

The antibacterial effect of organic acid mainly comes from its dissociation state in different pH environments as showed in Figure 2. When the ambient pH is lower than the value of organic acids, organic acids mainly exist in a undissociated state and can easily penetrate the lipid bimolecular cell

membrane of bacteria (Yang et al. 2019). Because the intracellular environment is close to neutral, organic acids dissociate and release many protons (H^+) after entering, resulting in acidification inside the cell (Lu et al. 2011). To maintain normal physiological function, bacteria must continuously excrete excess protons through the ATPase proton pump, which will consume a large amount of ATP, eventually leading to cell metabolic disorders and even death (Ricke 2003). Moreover, the acid radical anions remaining in the cell will also further inhibit the growth of bacteria by interfering with osmotic pressure and enzyme activity (Ji et al. 2023).

Figure 2. Proposed antimicrobial mechanisms of organic acids against bacterial cells. Undissociated organic acids diffuse across the bacterial cell membrane and dissociate in the near-neutral cytoplasm, leading to intracellular acidification. The release of protons increases the energy demand for proton extrusion through H^+ -ATPase, while accumulated acid anions may further disrupt membrane integrity, osmotic balance, enzyme activity, and DNA or protein synthesis. Adapted from Sorathiya et al. (2025).

1.5.2 Synergistic interactions between acids and bacteriocins

Organic acids mainly inhibit the growth of microorganisms by reducing the ambient pH, increasing the permeability of cell membranes and causing intracellular acidification. When the ambient pH is low, undissociated organic acids can more easily pass through the cell membrane into the cell and release H^+ in the cell, thus disturbing the intracellular pH stability and normal metabolic process.

Bacteriocins, on the other hand, mainly plays an antibacterial role by interacting with the bacterial cell membrane, forming membrane pores or interfering with cell wall synthesis. Many LAB bacteriocins will dissipate proton motive force (PMF) by forming membrane pores, leading to leakage of intracellular compounds such as ATP, amino acids and ions, eventually leading to cell death. Some bacteriocin, such as nisin, can also bind to lipid II to promote the formation of membrane pores while inhibiting cell wall synthesis, as illustrated in Figure 3, thus significantly enhancing the bactericidal activity. In this case, the membrane damage and intracellular acidification caused by organic acids can further promote the approach of bacteriocin to its target site, thus enhancing the membrane destruction ability of bacteriocin. At the same time, the membrane pores formed by bacteriocin will further accelerate the entry of H^+ and acid anions into cells, leading to more intracellular acidification and energy depletion. Therefore, this combined effect can result in stronger intracellular acidification, energy depletion, and ultimately a synergistic antibacterial effect (Pérez-Ramos et al. 2021).

Soltani et al. (2022) systematically studied the synergistic effects between lactic acid, citric acid and a variety of bacteriocins, and found that a variety of bacteriocin-organic acid combinations showed synergistic or partial synergistic inhibitory effects on Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. The study pointed out that when pediocin PA-1 was used in combination with lactic acid or citric acid, it showed obvious synergistic or partial synergistic effects on *Listeria ivanovii*. Similarly, nisin Z also showed some synergistic effects when combined with lactic acid or citric acid, leading to the MIC of bacteriocin being reduced to 1/2 or even 1/4 of the original, indicating that organic acids can significantly enhance the antibacterial activity of bacteriocin.

Figure 3. Scheme showing the mechanism of action for lantibiotic bacteriocins, mainly forming a pore into the target membrane by electrostatic interaction (wedge-like pores) or by binding to lipid II. Lipid II is formed in two steps: (i) the UDP-N-acetylmuramyl-pentapeptide is linked to the undecaprenyl phosphate by the enzyme MraY to obtain the lipid I; (ii) then, a unit of N-acetylglucosamine is linked to the N-acetylmuramyl by the enzyme MurG to obtain the final lipid II. After its formation, the lipid II is translocated across the membrane to the outer side, and oligomerized to form the cell wall. The cationic type-A lantibiotics (like nisin, depicted in the figure) can form a target-mediated pore using lipid II as a docking molecule. In addition, the hijacking of lipid II molecules for the formation of pores in the membrane can destabilise the formation of the wall, thereby weakening it. Adapted from Pérez-Ramos et al. (2021).

1.5.3 Modes of action on vegetative cells and endospores

Different stages of *Bacillus* have significantly different sensitivity to organic acids. For vegetative cells in the growing phase, organic acids and bacteriocin mainly cause their inactivation by destroying energy metabolism and cell membrane integrity (Lu et al. 2011). In contrast, *Bacillus* endospores have a higher tolerance to external stress due to its complex multi-layer structure, including spore coat, cortex and inner membrane. The acidic environment will first change the microenvironment around the spores, thus affecting the normal binding between nutrient germinants and germinant receptors. When spores cannot effectively perceive external nutritional signals, the germination process is difficult to start properly. In addition, low pH conditions will also interfere with the stability of the inner membrane and affect the activity of a variety of germination-related enzymes. Since spore germination depends on a series of highly coordinated physiological changes, acid stresses will

further interfere with Ca-DPA release, cortex degradation and subsequent core rehydration. As a result, the spores cannot germinate properly and return to vegetative cells (Setlow 2014).

1.5.4 Efficacy and limiting factors in food systems

When transforming the antibacterial strategy from laboratory culture medium to actual food application, the complex food matrix impact must be considered. For example, the rich protein and minerals in plant-based drinks may neutralize the hydrogen ions produced by organic acids, thus weakening its antibacterial effect. Secondly, the fat components in food may envelop spores or antibacterial substances, producing a spatial shielding effect. In addition, temperature fluctuations, oxygen content and natural antioxidants in plant components during processing may ultimately affect the stability of the inhibitory effect by changing the distribution balance of organic acids or the metabolic activity of LAB (Wang et al. 2024). Therefore, in practical applications, it is necessary to optimize the composition and ratio of antibacterial agents according to specific food formulas.

1.6 Faba bean

Legume crops have always been a sustainable source of high protein. Among legumes, faba bean (*Vicia faba*) is one of the oldest crops cultivated worldwide (Mínguez and Rubiales 2021). Mediterranean countries, Ethiopia, Egypt, China, Afganistan, India, Northeren Europe, and Northern Africa, are major producers of faba bean (Rahate et al. 2021). It can be a multiuse crop for food source, animal feed and fixation of atmospheric nitrogen (Zhou et al. 2018).

From the perspective of nutrition, mature seeds of faba bean are rich in proteins, carbohydrates, and dietary fiber. They also contain a variety of bioactive compounds such as total phenolics, and flavonoids (Valente et al. 2018). However, there are some antinutritional factors such as lectins, saponins, trypsin inhibitor, phytic acids, condensed tannins, and favism inducing factors, which negatively effect the biological value of faba bean (Revilla 2015). Consuming faba bean may lead to *favism*—a severe form of hemolytic anemia (Singh et al. 2013) and oligosaccharides in the faba bean may lead to flatulence and abdominal discomfort (Gupta et al. 2021). But as reported by studies, cooking, sprouting and fermentation can reduce many antinutritional factors in faba beans to improve the nutritional value of faba bean (Labba et al. 2021).

2 Material and methods

2.1 Bacterial strains and growth conditions

Table 1. Bacterial strains, isolation sources, and countries of origin used in this study.

Strain	Abbreviation	Source	Country
<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i> UFL ASAY 96	Lp. UFL ASAY 96	Brazilian industrial sausage	Brazil
<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i> 36h8h1	Lp. 36h8h1	mawè (fermented maize)	Benin
<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i> 0h9s1	Lp. 0h9s1	Nunu (fermented cow milk)	Ghana
<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i> 2-1	Lp. 2-1	mawè	Benin
<i>Limosilactobacillus fermentum</i> ZN1-10	Lf. ZN1-10	malted sorghum	Ghana
<i>Limosilactobacillus fermentum</i> 6h2.cm1	Lf. 6h2.cm1	mawè (fermented maize)	Benin
<i>Limosilactobacillus fermentum</i> ZN2-6	Lf. ZN2-6	Dolo (sorghum beer)	Ghana
<i>Limosilactobacillus fermentum</i> 12h5h1	Lf. 12h5h1	mawè	Benin
<i>Lactococcus lactis</i> MTIII-6.1.4	LL. MTIII-6.1.4	Lait caillé	Burkina Faso
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> BxFB-A B1	Bs.fb1	Dried faba beans	Norway
<i>Bacillus licheformis</i> BxFB-B B2	Bl.fb2	Dried faba beans	Norway
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> Natto	Bs.Natto	Commercial Natto spores product	Austria

MRS medium was used for *L. plantarum* and *L. fermentum* strains. GM-17 medium was used for *L. lactis* strain. BHI medium was used for *Bacillus* strains. The bacteria were stored at -60°C from a mid-exponential phase culture supplemented with glycerol 40% final. The overnight culture was prepared in two steps: first streaking the strain from the -60°C storage on the medium agar plate and being incubated overnight. Second, inoculating one colony from the plate into liquid medium tube and being incubated overnight. Tubes with LAB strains were put into 30°C incubator without shaking. Tubes with *Bacillus* strains were put in 30°C shaking incubator (200 rpm). Growth was monitored during the cultures by OD measurement of the bacterial suspension at 600 nm on a spectrophotometer.

2.2 Agar spot-lawn assay for screening LAB inhibitory activity

The overnight culture of LAB and *Bacillus* strains were prepared as described in 2.1. After being diluted to 0.1 of OD_{600 nm}, 3 µL of the diluted LAB culture were spotted on MRS and GM-17 plates and the plates were then incubated overnight again for LAB growing. Soft BHI agar (7%) containing the *Bacillus* (10⁵ CFU/mL) were poured onto the plates with LAB spots. The inhibition results would be detected by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone around the LAB spots.

The diameter D and d (as showed in the picture) of outer zone and inner LAB spot would be measured. The inhibition zone (A) would be calculated by the following equation:

Equation 1. Calculation of inhibition zone based on the diameters of the outer zone (D) and inner LAB spot (d).

$$A = \frac{\pi}{4} (D^2 - d^2)$$

2.3 Evaluation of LAB cell-free supernatants against *Bacillus* spp.

The overnight culture of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* UFLA SAY 96, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* 36h8h1, *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* ZN1-10, *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* 6h2.cm1, *Lactococcus lactis* MTIII-6.1.4 and three *Bacillus* strains were prepared as described in 2.1. After being cultured for 18 hours, the overnight culture of LAB strains were then transferred to 15 mL falcon tube, which would be centrifuged for 30 min at 5000 × g. The upper cell free supernatant in the falcon tube were collected and filtered through 0.22 µm film into new falcon tubes and then be stored on ice for use. The overnight culture of *Bacillus* strains were diluted into 0.1 at OD_{600nm}. 96 well plates were used in this experiment. A total of 200 µL liquid system was defined in each well. A series of 25%, 50% and 75% of supernatant concentration from different LAB strains were used to add into wells. And 20 µL diluted *Bacillus* culture was added into well. The positive control was well with 180 µL and 20 µL diluted *Bacillus* culture. The negative control was well with different concentration of supernatant and BHI broth. The 96 well plates were then put in 30°C incubator. After 24 and 48 hours, the OD_{600nm} of each well was measured. After 48 hours, the mixture in the well were

plated on BHI agar plates. The inhibition and growth of *Bacillus* would be detected by the OD_{600nm} values and the bacterial growth on BHI plate.

2.4 Well diffusion assay for detection of bacteriocin-like activity

The overnight culture of nine LAB strains and three *Bacillus* were prepared as described in 2.1. The bacteria overnight culture were transferred into 1 mL eppendorf tubes and then centrifuged (10000 × g, 4°C, 5 min). 500 µL of the supernatant were collected and filtered by 0.22 µm film into new eppendorf tubes. The filtered supernatant was added with 50 µL proteinase K (20 mg/mL). The mixed supernatant was then heated to 56°C for 30 min. After being heated, the mixed supernatant was put in fridge for storage. 6mL of soft BHI agar containing *Bacillus* (10⁵ CFU/mL) were poured onto the MRS and GM-17 plates. Wells were made after plates have dried. 40 µL of the mixed supernatant were put into the wells. Then the plates were put in 30°C incubator for 18 hours. The evaluation of bacteriocin-like substance would be measured by the appearance of inhibition zone around the wells.

2.5 Evaluation of pH tolerance of *Bacillus* spp.

The overnight culture of three *Bacillus* strains were prepared as described in 2.1. After being incubated for 18 hours at 30°C, the overnight cultures were diluted into 0.1 of OD_{600 nm}. Different pH levels of BHI broth (10 mL in tube) were prepared, adjusting by the HCl and NaOH. 100 µL of the diluted *Bacillus* cultures were transferred into BHI broth. The tubes were placed on the shaking incubator (200 × g, 30°C). The growth of *Bacillus* was detected by visual observation and their growth on the BHI plates.

2.6 Evaluation of organic acid inhibition against *Bacillus* spp.

The overnight culture of three *Bacillus* strains were prepared as described in 2.1. The overnight culture was diluted 100 fold and stored on ice for use. 20mM, 40mM, 60mM, and 80mM of lactic acid and acetic acid in BHI broth were prepared in fume hood. 180 µL organic acid under different concentrations and 20 µL diluted *Bacillus* culture were added into each well of 96 well plate. Each combination was conducted in triplicates. The plate would then be put in 30°C incubator. After 24 and 48 hours, the OD_{600nm} of were measured. After 48 hours, the mixture in the well were plated on BHI plates. The inhibition and growth of bacteria would be detected by the OD_{600nm} and the bacterial growth on BHI plate.

2.7 Faba bean fermentation with LAB strains

The faba bean powder was sterilized by UV radiation. 10 g of faba bean powder and 90 mL of demineralized water were added into the 250 mL flask. The overnight culture of LAB strains were prepared as described in 2.1. The inoculation volume of each LAB strains was calculated by the corresponding calibration curves to achieve a starting concentration of 10^5 CFU/mL. The flasks after being added with the start cultures, were then put into the shaking incubator (120 rpm, 30°C). At 0h, 6h, 24h, 30h, 48h, and 72h, the samples were taken out. The pH and bacterial growth at each time point would be recorded. The remaining of samples were collected for future HPLC analysis.

2.8 Determination of organic acids by HPLC

5 mL of sample from fermentation was mixed with 2.5 mL of 0.1 M potassium ferrocyanide trihydrate and 2.5 ml of 0.2 M zinc sulfate heptahydrate and centrifuged for 30 min at $5000 \times g$. The supernatant was collected in new falcon tubes and store at -20°C. Before HPLC, the supernatant was filtered through a 0.22 μm membrane and stored at -20°C before the analysis. Concentration of organic acids in the supernatants was determined by HPLC using an Aminex HPX-87H column (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Denmark) and a refractive index detector (RID; Agilent 1100 series, Waldbronn, Germany). Organic acid concentration was expressed in g per liter (g/L).

2.9 Data analysis and statistics

Statistical analyses were conducted using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to evaluate differences, with Least Squares Means differences (confidence level of 95 %), followed by Tukey's posthoc test. Letters were used to indicate statistically significant differences between groups in the figures.

3 Results

3.1 Inhibitory activity of LAB strains against *Bacillus* spp..

Figure 4. Inhibition zones produced by different LAB strains against *Bacillus subtilis* fb1 (Bs.fb1), *Bacillus licheniformis* fb2 (Bl.fb2) and *B. subtilis* natto (Bs.Natto). The tested LAB strains included *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* UFLA SAY 96 (Lp. UFLA SAY 96), *L. plantarum* 36h8h1 (Lp. 36h8h1), *L. plantarum* 0h9s1 (Lp. 0h9s1), *L. plantarum* 2-1 (Lp. 2-1), *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* ZN1-10 (Lf. ZN1-10), *L. fermentum* 6h2.cm1 (Lf. 6h2.cm1), *L. fermentum* ZN2-6 (Lf. ZN2-6), *L. fermentum* 12h5h1 (Lf. 12h5h1) and *Lactococcus lactis* MT III-6.1.4 (LL. MT III-6.1.4). Inhibition activity was determined by lawn assay and expressed as inhibition zone area (mm², mean ± SD). Different lowercase letters indicate statistically significant differences among LAB strains, as determined by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD post hoc test ($P \leq 0.05$).

As shown in Figure 1, different LAB strains exhibited varying levels of inhibitory activity against the three tested *Bacillus* strains (Bs.fb1, Bl.fb2 and Bs.Natto). In general, the inhibition of Bs.Natto was the strongest, followed by Bl.fb2, and Bs.fb1 was relatively the weakest.

Specifically, Lp. UFLA SAY 96, Lp. 36h8h1 and Lp. 0h9s1 showed the strongest antibacterial ability. Their inhibition area for Bs.Natto was in the range of about 350-400 mm², about 240-270 mm² for Bl.fb2, and about 200-230 mm² for Bs.fb1. These three strains were statistically marked with the same letter (a), significantly higher than other strains.

In contrast, the inhibitory ability of Lp. 2-1 and Lf. ZN1-10 decreased significantly. Lp. 2-1's inhibition of three strains of *Bacillus* was significantly reduced (about 40-130 mm²), while Lf. ZN1-10's inhibition of Bs.fb1 was extremely weak (about 30 mm²), but it still had a certain effect on Bs.Natto (about 220 mm²). These strains were usually labeled as b or c, indicating that they were significantly lower than the Lp. UFLA SAY 96/Lp. 36h8h1/Lp. 0h9s1 group. Lf. 6h2.cm1, Lf. ZN2-6 and Lf. 12h5h1 were at a medium level. The inhibition effect of Lf. 6h2.cm1 was more prominent, especially for Bs.Natto (about 260 mm²) and Bl.fb2 (about 180 mm²), which was close to the stronger group, while Lf. ZN2-6 and Lf. 12h5h1 further decreased, especially for Bs.fb1 with weak inhibition (about 50-80 mm²). *LL. MT III-6.1.4* had the lowest antibacterial ability, and the inhibition of three *Bacillus* strains were significantly weak (about 20-60 mm²) and were marked as the lowest significant group (c).

Figure 5. Inhibition zones produced by different LAB strains against *Bacillus subtilis* fb1 (Bs.fb1), *Bacillus licheniformis* fb2 (Bl.fb2) and *B. subtilis* natto (Bs.Natto) after 48 h incubation. The tested LAB strains included *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* UFLA SAY 96 (Lp. UFLA SAY 96), *L. plantarum* 36h8h1 (Lp. 36h8h1), *L. plantarum* 0h9s1 (Lp. 0h9s1), *L. plantarum* 2-1 (Lp. 2-1), *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* ZN1-10 (Lf. ZN1-10), *L. fermentum* 6h2.cm1 (Lf. 6h2.cm1), *L. fermentum* ZN2-6 (Lf. ZN2-6) and *L. fermentum* 12h5h1 (Lf. 12h5h1). Inhibition activity was determined by lawn assay and expressed as inhibition zone area (mm², mean \pm SD).

Figure 5 showed the inhibition zones produced by different LAB strains against the three tested *Bacillus* strains after 48 h of incubation. Compared with Figure 4, the inhibitory ability of all LAB

strains to *Bacillus* was significantly enhanced, and the overall area of the inhibition circle increased 2-3 times.

The inhibition of Bs.Natto was still the strongest, followed by Bl.fb2, the weakest to Bs.fb1. This pattern was consistent with Figure 1. Specifically, Lp. UFLA SAY 96 and Lp. 36h8h1 were still the most antibacterial strains. Inhibition of Lp. UFLA SAY 96 against Bs.Natto reached about 1400 mm², about 800 mm² for Bl.fb2, and about 500 mm² for Bs.fb1. Performance of Lp. 36h8h1 was similar or even higher for Bl.fb2 (about 1050 mm²). Lp. 0h9s1 and Lp. 2-1 also showed strong inhibition ability. Lp. 0h9s1 could reach about 1000 mm² for Bs.Natto, and about 600 mm² and 400 mm² for Bl.fb2 and Bs.fb1 respectively. Although Lp. 2-1 was weak in Figure 1, it was significantly enhanced after 48h, especially for Bs. Natto (about 900 mm²).

The performance of Lf. ZN1-10 was more special. Its inhibition of Bl.fb2 and Bs.Natto were strong (about 700 mm²), but it was still weak on Bs.fb1 (about 280 mm²). Lf. 6h2.cm1, Lf. ZN2-6 and Lf. 12h5h1 were generally at a medium-low level.

Lf. 6h2.cm1 increased for all three bacteria (about 300-600 mm²), but lower than the Lp group. Lf. ZN2-6 and Lf. 12h5h1 further decreased, among which the overall inhibition ability of Lf. 12h5h1 was weaker, especially for Bs.fb1.

3.2 Inhibitory effects of LAB cell-free supernatants against *Bacillus* spp.

Figure 6. Heatmap showing the OD values of different concentrations of LAB cell-free supernatants against *Bacillus subtilis* fb1 (Bs.fb1), *Bacillus licheniformis* fb2 (Bl.fb2) and *B. subtilis* natto (Bs.Natto) at 0 h. The tested LAB strains included *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* UFLA SAY 96 (Lp. UFLA SAY 96), *L. plantarum* 36h8h1 (Lp. 36h8h1), *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* ZN1-10 (Lf. ZN1-10), *L. fermentum* 6h2.cm1 (Lf. 6h2.cm1) and *Lactococcus lactis* MT III-6.1.4 (LL. MT III-6.1.4). Different percentages indicate different concentrations of LAB cell-free supernatants.

Figure 7. Heatmaps showing the OD values of different concentrations of LAB cell-free supernatants against *Bacillus subtilis* fb1 (Bs.fb1), *Bacillus licheniformis* fb2 (Bl.fb2) and *B. subtilis* N atto (Bs.Natto) after 24 h and 48 h incubation. The tested LAB strains included *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* UFLA SAY 96 (Lp. UFLA SAY 96), *L. plantarum* 36h8h1 (Lp. 36h8h1), *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* ZN1-10 (Lf. ZN1-10), *L. fermentum* 6h2.cm1 (Lf. 6h2.cm1) and *Lactococcus lactis* MT III-6.1.4 (LL. MT III-6.1.4). Different percentages indicate different concentrations of LAB cell-free supernatants. Lower OD values indicate stronger inhibitory activity against *Bacillus* strains.

Figure 6 showed the initial OD₆₀₀ nm values of different concentrations of LAB cell-free supernatants against the three tested *Bacillus* strains at 0 h, while Figure 7 showed the changes in OD₆₀₀ nm after 24 and 48 h of incubation. The results showed that different LAB strains and their different concentrations of supernatant had different performance of inhibitory effects on the growth of three *Bacillus* strains (Bs.fb1, Bl.fb2 and Bs.Natto) after 24 h and 48 h culture. The colour depth and the corresponding value in the figure represented the size of the OD value, of which the lower OD value represented a stronger antibacterial effect.

At 24 hours, there had already been a significant difference between different treatments. The lower concentration of LAB supernatant had a weak antibacterial effect, while the higher concentration of

supernatant showed stronger inhibition ability. Among them, the OD value of Lf. ZN1-10 25% treatment was the highest, and the OD values of Bs.fb1, Bl.fb2 and Bs.Natto reached 1.80, 1.27 and 0.96 respectively, indicating that bacteria still maintained strong growth activity under these conditions. Similarly, *LL. MT III-6.1.4* 25% also showed a high OD value, indicating that its antibacterial effect was limited. In contrast, a higher concentration of LAB supernatant significantly inhibited the growth of three *Bacillus* strains. For example, the OD values of *LL. MT III-6.1.4* 75%, Lf. 6h2.cm1 75%, Lf. ZN1-10 75%, Lf. 6h2.cm1 50%, Lf. ZN1-10 50% and all Lp. UFLA SAY 96 and Lp. 36h8h1 treatment groups were maintained between 0.07–0.11, indicating that these treatments almost completely inhibited bacterial growth.

At 48 h, the overall trend was similar to that at 24 h, but the OD value of some treatment groups was further increased compared with that at 24 h. Among them, Lf. ZN1-10 25% still showed the weakest antibacterial effect, and its OD values for Bs.fb1, Bl.fb2 and Bs.Natto reached 1.88, 1.80 and 2.03 respectively. The *LL. MT III-6.1.4* 25% and *LL. MT III-6.1.4* 50% treatment groups also maintained a high OD value, indicating that their antibacterial ability was relatively weak. In contrast, the different concentration treatments of Lp. UFLA SAY 96 and Lp. 36h8h1 still maintained low OD values (about 0.07–0.08) at 48 h.

In general, the antibacterial effect of LAB supernatant showed obvious strain dependence and concentration dependence. As the concentration of supernatant increased, its inhibitory effect on *Bacillus* growth was generally enhanced. Among them, Lp. UFLA SAY 96 and Lp. 36h8h1 showed the most stable and significant antibacterial ability at both 24 h and 48 h.

3.3 Detection of bacteriocin-like activity

Figure 8. The inhibitory activity of cell-free supernatants from different *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* strains against *Bacillus subtilis natto*. The left well in each panel contained proteinase K-treated supernatant, while the right well contained untreated supernatant. Soft agar lawns were prepared with *Bs. natto*. Panels A–D correspond to LAB strains *L. plantarum* UFLA SAY 96, *L. plantarum* 36h8h1, *L. plantarum* 0h9s1, and *L. plantarum* 2-1, respectively. Inhibition zones surrounding the wells indicate inhibitory activity. Scale bar = 10 mm.

Figure 8 showed the inhibitory activity of cell-free supernatants (with and without proteinase K treatment) from selected *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* strains against *Bs. Natto*. Among them, the Lp. 2-1 strain (Figure 8D) showed the strongest antibacterial activity. A wide and inhibition zone of inhibition was formed around its untreated supernatant (right well), and the inhibition zone completely disappeared after proteinase K treatment (left well). The untreated supernatant of the Lp. 36h8h1 strain (Figure 8B) also showed an obvious inhibition zone, and the zone shrank significantly after proteinase K treatment. In contrast, the untreated supernatant of the Lp. UFLA SAY 96 (Figure 8A) and Lp. 0h9s1 (Figure 8C) strains only showed weak antibacterial activity, and there was no obvious change in the antibacterial effect after proteinase K treatment. There was only a slight inhibition of bacterial growth or morphological changes around the well.

3.4 pH tolerance of *Bacillus* spp.

Table 2. Growth response of different *Bacillus* strains under various pH conditions in BHI broth and on BHI agar. +++: abundant growth; ++: moderate growth; +: visible/limited growth; -: no detectable growth; —: not tested.

Strain	Medium	pH 6.8	pH 6.5	pH 6.0	pH 5.6	pH 5.1	pH 4.5	pH 4.1	pH 3.5
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> fb1	BHI broth	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> fb1	BHI agar	—	—	—	+++	+++	+	-	-
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> fb2	BHI broth	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> fb2	BHI agar	—	—	—	+++	++	++	-	-
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> Natto	BHI broth	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> Natto	BHI agar	—	—	—	+++	++	-	-	-

Table 2 showed the growth of three *Bacillus* strains after culture under different pH conditions. In general, with the decrease of pH, the growth of the three strains in BHI broth gradually weakened, and the growth of *Bacillus* on BHI agar after different pH conditions also showed a downward trend as showed in Appendix 3.

In BHI broth, *Bacillus subtilis* fb1 showed visible growth (+) at pH 6.8, 6.5, 6.0, 5.6 and 5.1, and no growth was observed below pH 4.5, 4.1 and 3.5 (-). The results of *Bacillus licheniformis* fb2 were similar to those of *B. subtilis* fb1. There was visible growth at pH 6.8 to 5.1, but no growth was observed below pH 4.5. *B. subtilis* Natto also showed growth at pH 6.8, 6.5, 6.0, 5.6 and 5.1, and no growth was observed at pH 4.5, 4.1 and 3.5.

After spreading the bacterial solution cultured under different pH conditions to BHI agar, the three strains showed different degrees of colony growth under different treatment conditions. For *B. subtilis* fb1, the bacterial solution treated with pH 5.6 showed abundant growth on the plate (+++), after pH 5.1 treatment showed moderate growth (++), and only limited visible growth was observed after pH 4.5 (+). No colony growth was observed at pH 6.8, 6.5, 6.0, 4.1 and 3.5 (-).

For *B. licheniformis* fb2, the bacterial solution treated with pH 5.6 also showed abundant growth (+++). Moderate growth was observed at pH 5.1 and pH 4.5 (++). No growth was observed at pH 6.8, 6.5, 6.0, 4.1 and 3.5.

For *B. subtilis* natto, the bacterial liquid after pH 5.6 treatment showed abundant growth (+++), and after pH 5.1 treatment, it showed moderate growth (++). No colony growth was observed at pH 6.8, 6.5, 6.0, 4.5, 4.1 and 3.5 (-). 3.4 Inhibition of organic acids of *Bacillus* spp.

3.5 Inhibitory effects of organic acids against *Bacillus* spp.

Figure 9. Heatmap showing the effects of different lactic acid concentrations on the growth of *Bacillus subtilis* fb1 (Bs.fb1), *Bacillus licheniformis* fb2 (Bl.fb2) and *B. subtilis* natto (Bs.Natto) after 0 h, 24 h and 48 h incubation. OD values were used to evaluate bacterial growth under different lactic acid concentrations (20–80 mM). Lower OD values indicate stronger inhibitory effects. Different lowercase letters indicate statistically significant differences among incubation times within the same lactic acid concentration, as determined by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s HSD post hoc test ($P \leq 0.05$).

Figure 9 showed the effect of different concentrations of lactic acid (20, 40, 60 and 80 mM) on the growth of three *Bacillus* strains (Bs.fb1, Bl.fb2 and Bs.Natto) at different incubation times (0, 24 and 48 h). The color shade and the numerical value in the figure represented the OD value measured under the corresponding conditions. The higher the OD value, the stronger the cell growth signal detected under this condition.

At 0 h, the OD values of the three bacteria at different lactic acid concentrations were generally lower and the difference was very small, and most of the values were concentrated between 0.11–0.12. Bs.fb1 was 0.12 at 20, 40, 60 and 80 mM; Bl.fb2 was slightly lower at 40 mM, 0.11, and the rest was 0.12; Bs.Natto was also 0.11 at 40 mM, and 0.12 at the rest of the conditions.

At 24 h, the OD value of the 20 mM group was significantly higher than that of the rest of the concentration group. Bs.fb1 reached 1.57 at 20 mM, while 0.08, 0.08 and 0.09 at 40, 60 and 80 mM respectively. Bl.fb2 was 0.82 at 20 mM, and the rest of the concentration was maintained between 0.08–0.09. Bs.Natto was 0.84 at 20 mM, 0.08 at 40 and 60 mM, and 0.10 at 80 mM.

At 48 h, the OD value of the 20 mM group increased further. Bs.fb1 reached 1.63 at 20 mM, dropped to 0.47 at 40 mM, and 0.09 at 60 and 80 mM. Bl.fb2 was 1.27 at 20 mM, and 0.09, 0.09 and 0.10 at 40, 60 and 80 mM respectively. Bs.Natto was 1.41 at 20 mM, and 0.08, 0.09 and 0.12 at 40, 60 and 80 mM respectively.

Overall, the OD value of the three strains under the condition of 20 mM lactic acid was significantly higher than that of the 40–80 mM group, and the OD value continued to increase between 24 h and 48 h, while the OD value of the 40–80 mM group at various points in time was generally maintained at a low level.

Figure 10. Heatmap showing the effects of different acetic acid concentrations on the growth of *Bacillus subtilis* fb1 (Bs.fb1), *Bacillus licheniformis* fb2 (Bl.fb2) and *B. subtilis* natto (Bs.Natto) after 0 h, 24 h and 48 h incubation. OD values were used to evaluate bacterial growth under different acetic acid concentrations (20–80 mM). Lower OD values indicate stronger inhibitory effects. Different lowercase letters indicate statistically significant differences among incubation times within the same acetic acid concentration, as determined by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s HSD post hoc test ($P \leq 0.05$).

Figure 10 showed the effect of different concentrations of acetic acid (20, 40, 60 and 80 mM) on the growth of three *Bacillus* strains (Bs.fb1, Bl.fb2 and Bs.Natto) at different culture times (0, 24 and 48 h). The color shade and the corresponding value in the figure represented the OD value measured under the corresponding conditions. The higher the OD value, the stronger the detected cell growth signal.

At 0 h, the OD value of the three bacteria under different acetic acid concentrations was generally low and the difference was very small, and most of the values were concentrated between 0.11–0.12. Bs.fb1 was 0.12 at 20, 60 and 80 mM, and 0.11 at 40 mM; Bl.fb2 was 0.12 at 20 and 80 mM, and 0.11 at 40 and 60 mM; Bs.Natto was 0.12 under 20, 60 and 80 mM, and 0.11 under 40 mM.

At 24 h, the OD value of the 20 mM group was higher than that of the rest of the concentration group. Bs.fb1 reached 1.45 at 20 mM, while 0.08 at 40, 60 and 80 mM. Bl.fb2 was 0.61 at 20 mM, while 0.08 at 40 and 60 mM, and 0.09 at 80 mM. Bs.Natto was only 0.14 at 20 mM, 0.08 at 40 and 60 mM, and 0.09 at 80 mM.

At 48 h, the OD value of the 20 mM group increased further. Bs.fb1 reached 1.70 at 20 mM, and remained at 0.08 at 40, 60 and 80 mM. Bl.fb2 was 1.20 at 20 mM, while 0.08 at 40 and 60 mM, and 0.09 at 80 mM. Bs.Natto was 0.27 at 20 mM, 0.08 at 40 and 60 mM, and 0.11 at 80 mM.

Overall, the OD value of the three bacteria under the condition of 40-80 mM acetic acid was maintained at a low level at each point in time, while the 20 mM group showed a higher OD value at 24 h and 48 h. Among them, the OD value of Bs.fb1 and Bl.fb2 under the condition of 20 mM increased significantly with the increase of incubation time, while the increase in the OD value of Bs.Natto under the same condition was relatively small.

3.6 Faba bean fermentation with LAB strains

3.6.1 pH changes during faba bean fermentation

Figure 11. Changes in pH during faba bean fermentation inoculated with different LAB strains over 72 h. The tested strains included *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* 36h8h1 (Lp. 36h8h1), *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*

6h2.cm1 (Lf. 6h2.cm1) and *Lactococcus lactis* MT III-6.1.4 (LL. MT III-6.1.4), together with a non-inoculated control. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Different lowercase letters indicate statistically significant differences over fermentation time within the same treatment group, as determined by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD post hoc test ($P \leq 0.05$).

Figure 11 showed the changing trend of pH of faba bean powder medium during the fermentation with different LAB strains. The pH of the control group that was not inoculated with LAB remained basically stable during the whole 72h fermentation process, always around 6.2. In contrast, the three treatment groups of inoculated LAB strains showed different degrees of pH decline. Among them, *LL. MT III-6.1.4* showed an acidification effect in the early stage of fermentation, and the pH dropped from about 6.2 at 0h to about 5.3 at 6h, and then further dropped to about 4.8 at 24h, and remained in the range of about 4.5-4.9 between 30-72h.

The pH of *Lf. 6h2.cm1* had almost no significant change between 0-6h and still maintained at about 6.1-6.2. but it quickly dropped to about 4.4 at 24 h, and then remains between about 4.4-4.7 at 30-72 h. *Lp. 36h8h1* showed the strongest acidification ability. The pH was still close to the initial level between 0-6 h, but dropped sharply to about 4.1 at 24 h, and continued to maintain a lower level at 30 h and 48 h, reaching the lowest value at 48 h, about 4.0. By 72h, the pH of *Lp. 36h8h1* rose to about 4.4, but it was still significantly lower than that of the control group..

Judging from the significance annotation, there was no obvious difference between the groups at 0 h. By 6h, the pH of *LL. MT III-6.1.4* was significantly lower than that of other groups, while *Lf. 6h2.cm1*, *Lp. 36h8h1* and the control group were still at a similar level. After 24h, the pH of all LAB treatment groups was significantly lower than that of the control group. Among them, *Lp. 36h8h1* was usually at the lowest pH level, especially the acidification effect is most obvious in the 24-48h stage.

Therefore, the results showed that the LAB strain could effectively reduce the pH of the faba bean powder fermentation system, but there were obvious differences in the acidification rate and final acidification degree of different strains. *LL. MT III-6.1.4* acidification started earlier, *Lf. 6h2.cm1* acidified later but decreased significantly, while *Lp. 36h8h1* showed the strongest overall acidification ability.

3.6.2 Growth of LAB during faba bean fermentation

Figure 12. Growth of different LAB strains during faba bean fermentation over 72 h. The tested strains included *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* 36h8h1 (Lp. 36h8h1), *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* 6h2.cm1 (Lf. 6h2.cm1) and *Lactococcus lactis* MT III-6.1.4 (LL. MT III-6.1.4). Bacterial growth was expressed as log₁₀ CFU/mL. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Different lowercase letters indicate statistically significant differences over fermentation time within the same treatment group, as determined by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD post hoc test ($P \leq 0.05$)

Figure 12 showed the growth changes of three LAB strains during faba bean fermentation over 72 h. At 0 h, the initial number of bacteria of the three strains was about 10^5 CFU/mL, of which LL. MT III-6.1.4 and Lf. 6h2.cm1 were slightly higher than Lp. 36h8h1. After 6 hours of fermentation, the number of live bacteria of the three strains increased significantly. LL. MT III-6.1.4 and Lf. 6h2.cm1 were close to 10^9 CFU/mL, while Lp. 36h8h1 was about 10^8 CFU/mL. When fermentation continued to 24 h and 30 h, the number of three strains increased further and basically maintained around about 10^{10} CFU/mL. Among them, the value of LL. MT III-6.1.4 at these two points in time is always slightly higher than that of the other two strains.

At 48 h, LL. MT III-6.1.4 reached the highest value in the whole fermentation process, slightly higher than 10^{10} CFU/mL, while the number of bacteria in Lf. 6h2.cm1 and Lp. 36h8h1 was slightly lower,

but the overall level was still maintained at a high level. By 72 h, the number of live bacteria of the three strains decreased slightly, but the whole was still in the range of about 10^9 - 10^{10} CFU/mL, of which LL. MT III-6.1.4 still maintained the highest level.

3.6.3 Organic acid production during faba bean fermentation

Figure 13. Changes in lactic acid concentration during faba bean fermentation inoculated with different LAB strains over 72 h. The tested strains included *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* 36h8h1 (Lp. 36h8h1), *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* 6h2.cm1 (Lf. 6h2.cm1) and *Lactococcus lactis* MT III-6.1.4 (LL. MT III-6.1.4), together with a non-inoculated control. Lactic acid concentration was determined by HPLC and expressed as g/L. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Different lowercase letters indicate statistically significant differences among treatment groups at the same fermentation time, as determined by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD post hoc test ($P \leq 0.05$).

Figure 13 showed the changes in lactic acid concentration during faba bean fermentation inoculated with different LAB strains over 72 h. Lp. 36h8h1 had the strongest ability to produce lactic acid, followed by Lf. 6h2.cm1, while LL. MT III-6.1.4 only produced a small amount of lactic acid in the early stage of fermentation, and then the lactic acid content had been maintained at a low level. There was almost no lactic acid accumulation in the control group.

At 0h, the lactic acid content of all treatment groups was close to 0 g/L. As fermentation progressed, Lp. 36h8h1 showed the most obvious trend of lactic acid accumulation. During 0-6 h, the Lp. 36h8h1 lactic acid content was still low, but it rose rapidly between 6-24h, reaching about 3.0 g/L in 24h, and further rose to the highest value at 30h, about 3.1-3.2 g/L. After that, the lactic acid content of Lp. 36h8h1 began to decline, dropping to about 2.5 g/L for 48h, and further dropping to about 0.7 g/L for 72h.

Lactic acid production of Lf. 6h2.cm1 also occurred mainly between 6-24h. Its lactic acid content was close to 0 g/L at 0h and 6h, then increased to about 1.0 g/L at 24h, and reached about 1.1 g/L at 30 h. After that, the lactic acid content of Lf. 6h2.cm1 was basically maintained at about 1.0 g/L and remained at about 1.1 g/L by 72 h. Compared with Lp. 36h8h1, the lactic acid accumulation of Lf. 6h2.cm1 was significantly lower.

The lactic acid change pattern of LL. MT III-6.1.4 is different from that of Lp. 36h8h1 and Lf. 6h2.cm1. Its lactic acid content increased to about 0.6-0.7 g/L at 6h, however, from 24h, the lactic acid content decreased rapidly and remained at about 0.1 g/L, which was still at a low level until 72h. The lactic acid content of the control group was always close to 0 g/L throughout the whole process.

Judging from the significance labelling, the lactic acid content of Lp. 36h8h1 at 24h, 30h and 48h was significantly higher than that of other treatment groups. Lf. 6h2.cm1 also showed higher lactic acid levels than those in the control group and LL. MT III-6.1.4 after 24h, but lower than Lp. 36h8h1. Although the lactic acid content of LL. MT III-6.1.4 increased significantly at 6 h, it was close to the control group in the later stage.

Overall, Lp. 36h8h1 was the strongest lactic acid production strain, which could reach the peak of lactic acid accumulation in 24-30 h. Lf. 6h2.cm1's acid production capacity was moderate and relatively stable in the later stage. While LL. MT III-6.1.4 mainly produced lactic acid briefly in the early stage, and then the lactic acid level decreased significantly.

Figure 14. Changes in acetic acid concentration during faba bean fermentation inoculated with different LAB strains over 72 h. The tested strains included *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* 36h8h1 (Lp. 36h8h1), *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* 6h2.cm1 (Lf. 6h2.cm1) and *Lactococcus lactis* MT III-6.1.4 (LL. MT III-6.1.4), together with a non-inoculated control. Acetic acid concentration was determined by HPLC and expressed as g/L. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Different lowercase letters indicate statistically significant differences among treatment groups at the same fermentation time, as determined by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD post hoc test ($P \leq 0.05$).

Figure 14 showed that different LAB strains exhibited distinct acetic acid production patterns during faba bean fermentation over 72 h. Among the LAB strains, Lp. 36h8h1 showed the strongest acetic acid production ability in the later stage, while Lf. 6h2.cm1 and LL. MT III-6.1.4 showed a relatively mild and stable upward trend, and the control group had always maintained a very low level.

In the early stage of fermentation (0-6h), the acetic acid content of all treatment groups was close to 0 g/L. Between 6-24 h, the acetic acid content of Lf. 6h2.cm1 and LL. MT III-6.1.4 rose rapidly, reaching about 0.9-1.0 g/L at 24 h, and there was no significant difference between the two. At this stage, the acetic acid content of Lp. 36h8h1 only increased slightly to about 0.3 g/L, which was significantly lower than that of Lf. 6h2.cm1 and LL. MT III-6.1.4.

During 24-30 h, the acetic acid content of Lf. 6h2.cm1 and LL. MT III–6.1.4 continued to rise slowly, reaching about 1.1-1.2 g/L and about 1.0 g/L respectively, while Lp. 36h8h1 remained at a low level (about 0.4-0.5 g/L). At this stage, the difference between the three was more obvious, and Lp. 36h8h1 was significantly lower than that of the other two strains.

Entering the late stage (30-72 h), the production of acetic acid of Lp. 36h8h1 was significantly enhanced. Its acetic acid content rose rapidly to about 1.2 g/L between 30-48 h, and reached the highest value at 72 h, about 2.5 g/L, significantly higher than all other treatment groups. In contrast, the acetic acid content of Lf. 6h2.cm1 rose slowly between 30-72h, from about 1.2 g/L to about 1.5 g/L, showing a stable but limited growth trend. the acetic acid content of LL. MT III–6.1.4 basically stabilized after 30 h, at 48-72h was maintained between about 1.2-1.3 g/L, with slight change.

From the analysis of significance, in the late fermentation stage (especially 72h), the acetic acid content of Lp. 36h8h1 was significantly higher than that of all other treatment groups. Lf. 6h2.cm1 is usually higher than or close to LL. MT III–6.1.4, but the difference between the two was not as obvious as that of Lp. 36h8h1.

In summary, LL. MT III–6.1.4 and Lf. 6h2.cm1 began to produce acetic acid in the early and middle stages of fermentation and gradually stabilized, while Lp. 36h8h1 significantly enhanced acetic acid production in the later stage of fermentation and finally reached the highest level.

4 Discussion

4.1 Strain-dependent inhibitory activity of LAB against *Bacillus* spp.

The results of lawn assay in this study showed that different LAB strains could have different performance of inhibitory effects on the three *Bacillus* strains. Studies in recent years have shown that the antibacterial effect of LAB mainly comes from the organic acids, bacteriocins, hydrogen peroxide and other diffusible metabolites as described in 1.5, which can diffuse from the LAB growth area to the surrounding and upper soft agar, forming an environment that is not suitable to the growth of *Bacillus*, thus forming a transparent inhibition zone. However, since lawn assay is essentially a diffusion-based detection method, the diffusion of metabolites in agar will directly affect the area of the inhibition zone formed in the end. Lactic acid, acetic acid and other small molecule organic acids have strong diffusion ability, so it is easier to form a large transparent circle with clear boundaries in agar, while some protein antibacterial substances, such as bacteriocin, may be limited to a certain

extent due to their large molecular weight, even if they have strong antibacterial activity (Hoover and Harlander 1993).

In addition to the direct effect of antibacterial metabolites, LAB may also have inhibited the growth of *Bacillus* through ecological competition mechanisms in the lawn assay. Studies have shown that microbes generally compete for environmental nutrients in two ways. The first is through passive competition, namely exploitation, and the second is by severe competition. Species compete directly for resources, with one species demonstrating higher consumption of resources and thus limiting the other. The second type of competition is direct competition (interference competition), whereby individual cells harm each other by positioning themselves in a state to ward off already established competitors or to entirely destroy competitors, as well as through territorial colonization, especially in uninhabited areas (Siedler et al. 2019). In this experiment, LAB first grew on the bottom agar medium. Before *Bacillus* was added to the upper soft agar, LAB had time to utilize the available carbon, nitrogen, amino acids, vitamins and minerals in the surrounding environment. As LAB continued to grow, the available nutrients in the surrounding area gradually decreased. For *Bacillus* subsequently covered in the soft agar, the location near the LAB growth area was no longer a fresh nutritional environment, but a microenvironment that had been partially consumed by LAB. Therefore, even if *Bacillus* itself had the ability to grow, it may have been difficult for *Bacillus* to form normal colony growth in areas close to LAB due to the lack of available nutrients.

Among all the test LAB strains, Lp. UFLA SAY 96, Lp. 36h8h1 and Lp. 0h9s1 showed the strongest antibacterial ability, while the antibacterial effect of other LAB strains was relatively weak, indicating that the antibacterial ability of LAB has obvious strain specificity. Previous studies have shown that compared with most LAB, *L. plantarum* has a strong carbohydrate utilization system composed of a large number of sugar absorption and metabolism-related genes, which gives it strong carbohydrate utilization ability. The number of genes related to these sugar metabolism far exceeds that of other LAB genomes (Cui et al. 2021), which may contribute to enhanced organic acid production and antimicrobial activity. Therefore, Lp. UFLA SAY 96, Lp. 36h8h1 and Lp. 0h9s1 formed a larger inhibition zone, indicating that these plantarum strains can produce higher concentrations of diffusible antibacterial metabolites in the MRS medium or have stronger metabolic activity.

In contrast, LL. MT III-6.1.4 showed relatively weakest antibacterial ability. In addition to the metabolic characteristics of the strain itself, this result may also be related to the difference in culture medium. In this study, most LAB strains were cultured using MRS culture medium, while LL. MT

III-6.1.4 used GM-17 culture medium. Studies have shown that different culture medium composition would significantly affect the production of antibacterial metabolite such as bacteriocin (Wei et al. 2025).

Further comparison of the results after 24 h and 48 h incubation found that most LAB strains formed a larger inhibition zone after 48 h of culture, indicating that the antibacterial activity of LAB is obviously time dependent. With the extension of the incubation time, LAB would continue to accumulate antibacterial metabolites and the continuous diffusion of metabolites in agar may further expand the inhibition zone (Emmanuel Onyekachi Johnson et al. 2024).

Different *Bacillus* strains showed significantly different sensitivity to LAB inhibition. Among them, Bs.Natto showed the highest sensitivity in 24 h and 48 h experiments, while Bs.fb1 always showed strong tolerance. Since the organic acid produced by LAB is considered to be one of the important factors to inhibit the growth of *Bacillus* as described in 1.5, this difference may be related to the difference in acid tolerance between different *Bacillus* strains. Studies have shown that *Bacillus* can improve its survival ability in an acidic environment by regulating cell membrane composition, maintaining intracellular pH homeosis, and forming spores (Mols and Abee 2011). *Bacillus subtilis* has strong acid resistance, which is mainly related to its ability to quickly establish acid adaptation and maintain intracellular pH homeosis. In an acidic environment, *B. subtilis* will adjust related metabolic pathways such as dehydrogenase, decarboxylase and ethylation to reduce intracellular acid accumulation and promote proton excretion, thus alleviating acid stress. At the same time, it will also activate oxidative stress and membrane steady-state-related systems, such as catalase and metal ion transport systems, to enhance the survival ability of cells under acidic conditions (Wilks et al. 2009). In this study, Bs.fb1 also showed high acid resistance in subsequent pH tolerance experiments, which further showed that the acid resistance may be related to its strong tolerance to LAB inhibition.

4.2 Role of LAB cell-free supernatants in *Bacillus* inhibition

Unlike lawn assay, this experiment did not involve the continuous growth of live LAB, so the antibacterial effect observed in the experiment mainly came from the metabolites that LAB had produced and accumulated in the supernatant during the incubation process. This allowed the experiment to more directly reflect the antibacterial ability of LAB extracellular metabolites themselves.

The results showed that there were obvious differences in the inhibitory effect of supernatant on *Bacillus* among different LAB strains, indicating that the composition of metabolites and their effective concentrations produced by different LAB strains might not have been the same. Even if they belonged to the same LAB family (like the *plantarum* strains and *fermentum* strains), there were still obvious strain differences in their antibacterial ability. Previous studies have also showed that different LAB strains may produce different levels and types of inhibitory metabolites (Ruiz Rodríguez et al. 2019).

In addition, the high-concentration supernatant group was more likely to maintain a lower OD value, while the low-concentration group was more likely to show *Bacillus* growth and recovery. This trend indicated that insufficient concentrations of antimicrobial compounds could not maintain sustained inhibition, allowing *Bacillus* to continue to proliferate. There has been studies showing that sublethal stress may not completely inhibit *Bacillus*, as some sublethally injured cells are still able to recover and resume growth under suitable conditions (Bevilacqua et al. 2020).

4.3 Possible contribution of bacteriocin-like antimicrobial compounds

In this project, the results of the well diffusion assay showed that not all tested LAB strains could form a significant inhibition zone against *Bacillus* strains. Although this experiment also tested strains of *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* and *Lactococcus lactis* strains, obvious antibacterial activity mainly appeared in some *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* strains, suggesting that bacteriocin-related antibacterial activity had strong strain specificity. This result was consistent with the study of Lauková et al., who isolated *L. plantarum* LP17L/1 from traditional sheep milk cheese and found that the strain carried 10 plantaricin-related genes, but its antibacterial spectrum was still not effective against all indicator bacteria. Instead, it mainly inhibited some *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Staphylococcus aureus* strains, and the concentrated antimicrobial substance inhibited 23 out of 31 indicator bacteria, accounting for 74.2%. This indicated that even if *L. plantarum* had the potential to produce bacteriocin, its actual antibacterial performance still depended on the specific strain and target bacteria, and not all LAB strains necessarily produced detectable bacteriocin (Lauková et al. 2022).

In this experiment, the untreated supernatant of Lp. 2-1 formed the most obvious inhibition zone in the *B. subtilis* natto lawn, and the inhibition zone almost completely disappeared after proteinase K treatment. This phenomenon suggested that the main antibacterial components of Lp. 2-1 were likely

bacteriocin-like compounds. The study of De Giani et al. on *L. plantarum* PBS067 provided similar evidence. The cell-free supernatant of this strain formed an inhibition zone in a well diffusion agar assay, and the authors further isolated a bacteriocin-like compound called plantaricin P1053. After proteinase K treatment, the antibacterial activity of this substance against *E. coli* was completely lost, indicating that the inhibitory activity depended on the protein/polypeptide nature of the compound (De Giani et al. 2019).

In contrast, Lp. 36h8h1 also formed a visible inhibition zone in the untreated supernatant, but the inhibition zone was only weakened rather than eliminated after proteinase K treatment. This suggested that the antibacterial activity of Lp. 36h8h1 might not have depended entirely on the same proteinaceous compound, and there might also have been some antimicrobial peptides that were not completely degraded or other antimicrobial factors that were not affected by proteinase K. However, since no further purification, mass spectrometry identification, or bacteriocin gene screening was performed in this experiment, a more appropriate interpretation was that Lp. 36h8h1 might have possessed bacteriocin-related activity, but the evidence was weaker than that for Lp. 2-1. In comparison, the inhibition zones of Lp. UFLA SAY 96 and Lp. 0h9s1 were weak, and no obvious changes were observed before and after proteinase K treatment, indicating that they did not show strong bacteriocin-like inhibition under the experimental conditions used in this study.

It is worth noting that although no obvious inhibition zone was observed in *L. fermentum* and LL. MT III–6.1.4 strains in this study, studies have shown that both types of LAB strains could also produce bacteriocins under specific conditions. For example, LL. MT III–6.1.4 was the main producer of the classical bacteriocin nisin, which had been widely used in food biopreservation (V. Dzhavakhiya et al. 2018), and some *L. fermentum* strains had also been reported to produce bacteriocin-like peptides with antibacterial activity (Riaz, Nawaz, and Hasnain 2010). However, the strains of *L. fermentum* and LL. MT III–6.1.4 tested in this experiment did not form a detectable inhibition zone under the current culture conditions and experimental system, indicating that bacteriocin expression might have been influenced by various factors such as strain background, medium composition, growth phase, and bacteriocin-related gene expression levels (Yang et al. 2018).

4.4 Effects of pH on *Bacillus* spp. growth

The results of this experiment showed that the three *Bacillus* strains could maintain a certain degree of growth in the range of pH 6.8–5.1, and when the pH dropped to 4.5 and below, their growth was

obviously limited, indicating that the low pH environment had a strong inhibitory effect on the growth of *Bacillus*.

Studies pointed out that *Bacillus subtilis* could usually maintain growth around pH 5.0, but its growth was quickly inhibited under lower pH conditions. When approaching the lowest growth pH 4.8, the cell proliferation rate decreased significantly. In this study, *B. subtilis* fb1 could still be observed to grow at pH 5.1, but no obvious growth could be observed in liquid medium below pH 4.5, which was similar to the result of the study (Gauvry et al. 2021).

For *Bacillus licheniformis*, the literature also showed that its suitable growth range was neutral, and its growth ability was significantly reduced under low pH conditions. Studies pointed out that the growth of *B. licheniformis* in an acidic food environment was usually restricted, and its minimum growth pH was generally close to 4.5–5.0. Especially in tomato juice (pH about 4.4), studies found that although some spores might still germinate, their growth capacity had been significantly reduced (Rodriguez, Cousin, and Nelson 1993). In this study, *B. licheniformis* fb2 still grew at pH 5.1, but the growth was basically unobservable below pH 4.5, which was similar to the results of previous study.

In addition, the acid tolerance of *B. subtilis* Natto in this project was slightly weaker than that of the other two strains, and no growth appeared earlier under low pH 4.5. This difference also showed that even if they belonged to the same species, there might still be obvious differences in acid tolerance between different strains. Similar strain-dependent differences were also observed in the literature. One study analysed the acid tolerance of different *Bacillus* isolates from traditional fermented foods, and the results showed that there were obvious differences in the survival rates of different strains in the same acid environment. For example, under the condition of pH 2, the survival rate of the strain NGA/NA/6 reached 52.37%, while the survival rate of NGA/NA/1 was only 17.58%, showing that there was a significant difference in acid resistance between different strains (Borthakur, et al. 2026).

4.5 Effects of organic acid on *Bacillus* spp. growth

The results of this study showed that both lactic acid and acetic acid could inhibit the growth of *Bacillus* spp., but there were significant differences between different organic acids, different concentrations and different strains. After 24 h and 48 h incubation, higher concentrations of organic acids usually corresponded to lower OD values, indicating that the growth of *Bacillus* was more strongly inhibited after the concentration of organic acids increased. In contrast, higher OD values could still be observed in the low-concentration treatment group, indicating that some strains could

still maintain growth under weak acid stress. This result was consistent with the conclusion in existing studies that organic acids were concentration-dependent on *Bacillus* antibacterial activity (Asensi et al. 1997a).

Studies found that acetic acid had an obvious bactericidal effect under low pH conditions: when the pH was 4.6, only 17.4 μM acetic acid could have a bactericidal effect on *B. subtilis*, and under pH 6, the antibacterial effect was significantly weakened. The author further used the intracellular pH fluorescent probe to find that acetic acid could quickly enter the cell and lead to a decrease in intracellular pH, while HCl under equal pH conditions did not produce the same effect, indicating that the transmembrane diffusion ability of weak organic acids was one of its important antibacterial mechanisms (Asensi et al. 1997b). In this project, the acetic acid treatment group also showed a significantly lower OD value at higher concentrations, which also supported this mechanism.

In addition, acetic acid in this study showed a more obvious antibacterial tendency than some lactic acid treatments, which might have been related to the high proportion of undissociated molecules of acetic acid. Asensi et al. (1997) also pointed out that under the condition of pH 4.6, about 44.5% of acetic acid existed in an undissociated state. The higher the undissociated state, the easier it was to pass through the cell membrane and release H^+ in the cell, thus destroying the intracellular pH homeostasis. Therefore, even if the external pH was similar, the antibacterial ability of different organic acids might still be different.

On the other hand, the results of this experiment also showed that the sensitivity of different *Bacillus* strains to organic acids was not consistent. For example, some strains still maintained a high level of OD under 40–80 mM conditions, while other strains had obvious growth restrictions under the same conditions. When Sun et al. (2021) studied the spore-forming bacteria in acidified sauces, they found that even under the condition of pH 4.4, if there was no organic acid, *B. subtilis* spores still had a high growth potential. However, after adding 0.3% acetic acid, it could be completely inhibited, and when 0.3% acetic acid was combined with 0.7% lactic acid, no growth was observed in the whole experimental range. This indicated that different *Bacillus* strains not only had a certain adaptability to low pH, but also the types and combinations of organic acids significantly affected the final antibacterial effect.

It was also worth noting that some treatment groups in this study had a lower OD at 24 h, and the OD increased again at 48 h, indicating that some cells might gradually resume growth after being

damaged by acid in the early stage. Weak acid usually first led to impaired cell metabolism, intracellular pH imbalance and increased ATP consumption, but some acid-resistant bacteria could gradually restore their growth capacity through mechanisms such as proton pump regulation, changes of membrane lipid composition and acid stress protein expression. Branson et al. (2022) found that under the treatment of organic acids with sub-bacteriostatic levels, bacteria accumulated acid anions and showed a decrease in intracellular pH, such as *Listeria monocytogenes*, whose intracellular pH could be reduced from 7.5 to 6.5, but the cells still activated defence mechanisms to maintain survival. Some of the OD recovery in this experiment might also have been related to similar acid adaptation processes.

4.6 Faba bean fermentation with LAB strains

4.6.1 pH changes and acidification

In this study, the pH of the control group that was not inoculated with LAB was basically maintained at about 6.2 during the 72h fermentation process, indicating that the system composed of faba bean powder and water itself did not undergo obvious acidification under the experimental conditions. In contrast, the three treatment groups inoculated with LAB showed different degrees of pH decline, indicating that LAB could grow and produce acidic metabolites in the faba bean system, thus reducing the pH. Verni et al. (2017) used 27 LAB strains isolated from faba bean sourdough to ferment faba bean dough respectively, and the results showed that the initial pH of the unfermented sample was 6.66, and after inoculation with different LAB strains, the pH at the endpoint of 24 h decreased to 4.91-5.78. The initial pH of the unfermented sample in this study was about 6.2. The pH of the LAB treatment group decreased to about 4.1-4.9 after 24 h, which was also consistent with the trend reported in the previous study.

Lp. 36h8h1 reduced the pH of the system to about 4.1 after 24 hours, indicating that it had a strong fermentation ability towards plant substrates. Similar results have also been observed in existing faba bean fermentation studies. Coda et al. (2015) used *L. plantarum* VTT E-133328 to ferment faba bean flour. After fermentation at 30°C for 24 hours, the pH of the system decreased from about 6.5 to about 4.2, which was aligned with result in this project, indicating that *L. plantarum* could quickly utilize the fermentable substrates in faba bean and produce a large amount of organic acids.

Lf. 6h2.cm1 showed almost no obvious acidification during 0–6 h, but the pH dropped rapidly to about 4.4 after 24 h, indicating that it might have required a longer adaptation period to the faba bean

system before starting rapid metabolism. Similar phenomena have also been reported in studies related to *L. fermentum*. Larsen et al. (2026) used *L. fermentum* NSB2 for fermentation in a faba bean protein concentrate fermentation, showing that the acidification rate of the *L. fermentum* strain in the early stage of fermentation was lower than that of *L. plantarum* strain.

In contrast, the LL. MT III–6.1.4 treatment group showed a more obvious early acidification phenomenon. The pH decreased from about 6.2 to 5.3 within 6 h, while Lp. 36h8h1 and Lf. 6h2.cm1 basically maintained the initial pH during the same period, indicating that LL. MT III–6.1.4 could start fermentation metabolism and accumulate lactic acid faster in the early stage. Studies have also pointed out that *L. lactis* had long been used as an important starter culture in the dairy industry. One of its core functions was to produce lactic acid at a relatively fast rate, thus promoting systemic acidification (Kondrotiene et al. 2023).

4.6.2 Growth dynamics of LAB strains

Three LAB strains showed obvious stage growth changes during the process of faba bean fermentation. 0-24 h was the most rapid period of bacterial growth, indicating that this stage was the main growing stage of LAB in the faba bean system, especially in the first 6 h. In the 24-48 h stage, the overall number of LAB tended to stabilize, and in the 48-72 h stage, the number of some strains decreased slightly. Similar growth patterns were also observed in other LAB dynamics studies. When studying the growth dynamics of multiple strains of *Lactobacillus*, Rezvani, et al. (2017) pointed out that most LABs experienced a shorter lag phase in the early stage of culture, and then entered the obvious exponential growth phase. After LAB reached a high cell density, the growth of bacteria gradually slowed down and entered the stationary phase. This phenomenon was usually related to the gradual consumption of nutrients and the continuous accumulation of metabolites such as lactic acid. With the extension of fermentation time, some LAB might gradually be affected by acid stress or nutrient depletion and began to enter the stage of slight decay.

4.6.3 Organic acid production and acidification

Lactiplantibacillus. plantarum 36h8h1

In this experiment, Lp. 36h8h1 showed significant lactic acid accumulation in the early stage of fermentation, while lactic acid gradually decreased and acetic acid continuously increased in the later stage. This change was highly consistent with the results of Bobillo and Marshall (1991) on the

metabolic transformation of *Lactobacillus plantarum*. The study pointed out that *L. plantarum* mainly produced lactic acid in the early stage of fermentation, but under prolonged incubation conditions, acetate production at the expense of lactate accumulated in earlier stages was observed. It further pointed out that under aerobic conditions, *L. plantarum* mainly metabolized sugars rapidly into lactic acid through the EMP pathway in the early stage. However, when glucose was gradually exhausted, the bacteria activated an oxygen-dependent lactate utilization pathway, allowing the accumulated lactic acid to be further converted into acetic acid. The authors suggested that this process might occur through the metabolic route of “lactate → pyruvate → acetyl-phosphate → acetate” as showed in Figure 15. This mechanism explained the changing trend of Lp. 36h8h1 in this study. In the early stage of fermentation, Lp. 36h8h1 rapidly accumulated lactic acid, indicating that the strain had strong sugar metabolism and acidification ability in the faba bean system. After entering the later stage, the lactic acid content decreased while acetic acid continuously increased, indicating that some lactic acid might not have continued to accumulate but was further reutilized and converted into acetic acid. This suggested that Lp. 36h8h1 did not always maintain typical homolactic fermentation but gradually shifted its metabolic flow in the later stage.

In addition, oxygen conditions might have further promoted this process. The authors found that under aerated conditions, acetic acid accumulated significantly in the later stage while lactic acid decreased. In contrast, under anaerobic conditions, lactic acid remained the main product. This study adopted 120 rpm shaking incubation, and there might have been a certain degree of oxygen exchange within the system. Therefore, the obvious increase of acetic acid in the later stage of Lp. 36h8h1 might also have been partially influenced by the microaerobic environment. The literature further pointed out that oxygen might induce the expression of related enzymes such as pyruvate oxidase and NADH-independent lactate dehydrogenase, thereby promoting the conversion of lactic acid into acetic acid.

Lactococcus. lactis MT III–6.1.4

In this study, the change trend of organic acid of LL. MT III–6.1.4 in the faba bean system was significantly different from that of Lp. 36h8h1. Lactic acid only accumulated briefly in the early stage of fermentation, and then maintained a low level, while acetic acid gradually increased and tended to stabilize in the middle and late stages. This showed that the metabolic pattern of LL. MT III–6.1.4 in the broad bean system might not have been fully manifested as typical continuous homolactic acid fermentation but gradually produced more mixed acid metabolic characteristics in the later stage.

This result was consistent with the study on the carbon source metabolism of *Lactococcus lactis*. The study of Thani et al. (2006) pointed out that when *L. lactis* used glucose as the only carbon source, it mainly conducted homolactic fermentation through the EMP pathway. Most of the carbon flow was converted into lactic acid, while the amount of acetic acid, formic acid and other by-products was at low level. However, the study also found that when *L. lactis* used xylose or mixed sugars, its metabolic pattern changed significantly. The authors pointed out that in xylose batch cultures, in addition to lactic acid, acetic acid and formic acid were also obviously produced. The authors believed that this was because xylose metabolism might partially proceed through heterolactic fermentation or mixed acid fermentation.

This mechanism might explain the organic acid changes of LL. MT III–6.1.4 in the faba bean system observed in this project. The composition of the usable carbon source in the faba bean system was obviously different from that of MRS (Landry et al. 2016). In addition to a small amount of fermentable glucose, faba bean also contained complex plant polysaccharides and some pentacarbon sugar sources. Therefore, LL. MT III–6.1.4 might not always have maintained the typical high-efficiency homolactic acid fermentation in the system but gradually showed partial mixed acid fermentation characteristics in the later stage, which led to the continuous accumulation of acetic acid.

Figure 15. Pathways for pyruvate conversion in lactic acid bacteria (LAB). A few features are highlighted: major pyruvate end-products are in bold uppercase; reactions resulting in ATP generation are in red, while those involving NAD⁺/NADH are in blue; oxygen is shown in a pale blue box. Pathways for glucose utilization: EMP, Emden–Meyerhof–Parnas pathway (homofermentative metabolism, green box); PK, phosphoketolase path-way (heterofermentative metabolism, brown box). Other metabolic pathways: tricarboxylic acid cycle (orange dashed line); citrate-to-pyruvate conversion (blue dashed line). Enzymes (alphabetic order) in metabolic pathways (black arrows): ACK, acetate kinase; ADHA/ADHE, acetaldehydedehydrogenase/alcohol dehydrogenase; ALD, a-acetolactate decarboxylase; ALS, a-acetolactate synthase; AR, acetoin reductase; BDH, butanedioldehydrogenase/diacetyl reductase; CL, citrate lyase; CS, citrate synthase; LDH, lactate dehydrogenase; LOX, lactate oxidase; MAE/MLE, malatedehydrogenase; OAD, oxaloacetate decarboxylase; PDH, pyruvate dehydrogenase; PFL, pyruvate formate lyase (PFL); pyruvate oxidase (POX); PTA, phosphotransacetylase; PYC, pyruvate carboxylase. Transporters: PTS (blue ellipse), sugar phosphotransferase system; ABC (grey square), ATP-binding cassette transporter; antiport/symport (grey rectangles), antiport or symport between sugars, ions and H⁺; citP (orange circles),

citrate permease transporter (a: symport with H^+ , slow citrate uptake; b: antiport with lactate, fast citrate uptake; c: antiport with citrate metabolic products, that is, pyruvate, α -acetolactate and acetate). Control of metabolic pathways: a schematic representation of Catabolite Carbon Repression is shown in the upper right section: F6P, fructose 6-phosphate; FBP, fructose 1,6-bisphosphate; P-Ser-Hpr, seryl-phosphorylated form of the phosphocarrier protein HPr; CcpA, carbon catabolite protein A; cre, catabolite-responsive element. Violet triangles, negative control; green triangles, positive control; grey rectangle, no significant control. Adapted from Zotta et al. 2017.

Limosilactobacillus fermentum 6h2.cm1

The lactic acid of *Lf.* 6h2.cm1 in the faba bean system had always been maintained at a low level, while acetic acid increased significantly in the later stage of fermentation. This trend was basically consistent with the typical heterofermentative metabolic characteristics of *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*. According to the literature, *L. fermentum* belonged to obligately heterofermentative LAB, and its metabolism mainly depended on the phosphoketolase pathway, which could simultaneously produce lactic acid, acetic acid and CO_2 , instead of mainly accumulating lactic acid like homofermentative lactic acid bacteria. In tomato mash fermentation, *L. fermentum* fermentation was accompanied by obvious acetic acid formation and formed typical heterolactic metabolic characteristics. In kimchi fermentation, it was also observed that *L. fermentum* could form a heterofermentative profile, accompanied by the generation of a variety of organic acids. (Farid et al. 2026).

Due to the absence of the key enzyme fructose-1,6-bisphosphate aldolase in the EMP pathway of *L. fermentum*, the glucose firstly would be metabolised into pentose phosphate and then split to form glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate and acetyl phosphate. Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate was then metabolized into lactic acid, while acetyl phosphate could be further converted into acetic acid (Hossain 2022). In this experiment, fermentation with *Lf.* 6h2.cm1 did not show obvious lactic acid accumulation, but gradually formed acetic acid accumulation, indicating that its carbon flow might have entered more metabolic branches related to acetyl phosphate. In addition, the literature pointed out that when acetyl phosphate further produced acetic acid instead of ethanol, bacteria could obtain additional ATP as showed in Figure 15 (Zotta et al. 2017).

5 Conclusion

This study systematically evaluated the inhibitory effect of different LAB strains on *Bacillus* spp. and explored their potential inhibitory mechanisms in combination with a faba bean fermentation model. The results showed that different LAB strains exhibited obvious differences in their inhibitory abilities against *Bacillus* spp. Among LAB strains, *L. plantarum* strains showed the strongest antimicrobial activity, whereas the inhibitory ability of *L. lactis* strain was relatively weak.

The results of the agar spot-lawn assay showed that Lp. UFLA SAY 96, Lp. 36h8h1 and Lp. 0h9s1 formed the largest inhibition zones and exhibited strong inhibitory effects against three *Bacillus* strains. The cell-free supernatant experiment further demonstrated that extracellular metabolites produced by LAB could effectively inhibit the growth of *Bacillus*, and the antimicrobial effect increased with increasing supernatant concentration. Lp. UFLA SAY 96 and Lp. 36h8h1 maintained low OD values under different concentration conditions, demonstrating stable and remarkable antimicrobial activity. The results of the well diffusion assay showed that the inhibitory activity of *L. plantarum* strains was significantly reduced or even disappeared after proteinase K treatment, indicating that proteinaceous antimicrobial substances might have been involved in inhibition of *Bacillus*. These findings suggested that, in addition to organic acids, bacteriocin-like substances might also have been important contributors to the antimicrobial activity.

The pH tolerance experiments showed that three *Bacillus* strains could maintain a certain degree of growth under weakly acidic conditions, and growth could still be observed at pH 5.1. However, when the pH decreased to 4.5 or below, their growth was significantly inhibited, indicating that environmental acidification was one of the important factors limiting the growth of *Bacillus*. Organic acid inhibition experiments further confirmed that both lactic acid and acetic acid could effectively inhibit the growth of *Bacillus*, and the antimicrobial effect increased significantly with increasing organic acid concentration. And acetic acid generally exhibited a stronger inhibitory effect than lactic acid, indicating that organic acids not only acted by reducing the environmental pH, but intracellular acidification caused by the entry of undissociated acid molecules into bacterial cells might also have contributed to the inhibition of bacterial growth.

In the faba bean fermentation system, all LAB strains caused a significant decrease in the pH of the system, indicating that these strains were able to adapt to the faba bean matrix and utilize its nutrients for metabolism. During fermentation, a clear accumulation of organic acids was observed, and

different strains exhibited distinct metabolic characteristics. The *L. plantarum* strain showed strong acidification ability, rapidly producing lactic acid and reducing the pH of the system, whereas *L. fermentum* showed a more pronounced tendency to accumulate acetic acid. Combined with the fermentation and antimicrobial results, it could be inferred that the inhibitory effect of LAB against *Bacillus* was not due to a single factor but rather resulted from the combined action of multiple mechanisms, including environmental acidification, organic acid accumulation, and bacteriocins produced by some LAB strains.

In summary, this study demonstrated that LAB had the potential to control the growth of *Bacillus* spp. in plant-based food systems, among which *L. plantarum* showed the greatest potential for bio preservation applications. The findings not only deepened the understanding of the mechanisms by which LAB inhibited *Bacillus* but also provided a theoretical basis for controlling *Bacillus* contamination in plant-based foods. In the future, further studies combining bacteriocin identification, metabolomic analysis and validation in actual food systems could provide deeper insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying the antimicrobial activity of LAB and promote their practical application in the plant-based food industry.

6 Literature

- Amina, Dellali, Zadi Karam Halima, and Karam Nour-Eddine. 2020. 'Lipase and Esterase Activities of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Different Biotopes'. *African Journal of Biotechnology* 19(4):156–64. doi:10.5897/AJB2020.17106.
- Asensi, Victor, Francisco Parra, Joshua Fierer, Eulalia Valle, Carmen Bordallo, Paz Rendueles, Santiago Gascón, José A. Carton, José A. Maradona, and José M. Arribas. 1997a. 'Bactericidal Effect of ADP and Acetic Acid on *Bacillus Subtilis*'. *Current Microbiology* 34(1):61–66. doi:10.1007/s002849900145.
- Asensi, Victor, Francisco Parra, Joshua Fierer, Eulalia Valle, Carmen Bordallo, Paz Rendueles, Santiago Gascón, José A. Carton, José A. Maradona, and José M. Arribas. 1997b. 'Bactericidal Effect of ADP and Acetic Acid on *Bacillus Subtilis*'. *Current Microbiology* 34(1):61–66. doi:10.1007/s002849900145.
- Barcenilla, Coral, Miroslav Ducic, Mercedes López, Miguel Prieto, and Avelino Álvarez-Ordóñez. 2022. 'Application of Lactic Acid Bacteria for the Biopreservation of Meat Products: A Systematic Review'. *Meat Science* 183:108661. doi:10.1016/j.meatsci.2021.108661.
- Barone, Rosario, Francesca Rappa, Filippo Macaluso, Celeste Caruso Bavisotto, Claudia Sangiorgi, Gaia Di Paola, Giovanni Tomasello, Valentina Di Felice, Vito Marcianò, Felicia Farina, Giovanni Zummo, Everly Conway De Macario, Alberto J. L. Macario, Massimo Cocchi, Francesco Cappello, and Antonella Marino Gammazza. 2016. 'Alcoholic Liver Disease: A Mouse Model Reveals Protection by *Lactobacillus Fermentum*'. *Clinical and Translational Gastroenterology* 7(1):e138. doi:10.1038/ctg.2015.66.
- Battelli, Giovanna, Paola Scano, Clara Albano, Laura R. Cagliani, Milena Brasca, and Roberto Consonni. 2019. 'Modifications of the Volatile and Nonvolatile Metabolome of Goat Cheese Due to Adjunct of Non-Starter Lactic Acid Bacteria'. *LWT* 116:108576. doi:10.1016/j.lwt.2019.108576.
- Bevilacqua, Antonio, Leonardo Petruzzi, Milena Sinigaglia, Barbara Speranza, Daniela Campaniello, Emanuela Ciuffreda, and Maria Rosaria Corbo. 2020. 'Effect of Physical and Chemical Treatments on Viability, Sub-Lethal Injury, and Release of Cellular Components from *Bacillus Clausii* and *Bacillus Coagulans* Spores and Cells'. *Foods* 9(12):1814. doi:10.3390/foods9121814.
- Bile salt hydrolase activity and cholesterol assimilation of lactic acid bacteria isolated from flowers. 2019. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science* 9(6):106–10. doi:10.7324/JAPS.2019.90615.
- Bobillo, Mercedes, and Valerie M. Marshall. 1991. 'Effect of Salt and Culture Aeration on Lactate and Acetate Production by *Lactobacillus Plantarum*'. *Food Microbiology* 8(2):153–60. doi:10.1016/0740-0020(91)90008-P.
- Borthakur, Debashree, Bipin Kumar Sharma, and Twesigye Duncan. 2026. 'Unravelling Functional *Bacillus* Strains from Ngari: A Step toward Sustainable Probiotic Applications in Food Systems'. *Annals of Microbiology* 76(1):19. doi:10.1186/s13213-026-01845-x.

- Branson, Savannah R., Jeff R. Broadbent, and Charles E. Carpenter. 2022. 'Internal pH and Acid Anion Accumulation in *Listeria Monocytogenes* and *Escherichia Coli* Exposed to Lactic or Acetic Acids at Mildly Acidic pH'. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 12:803271. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2021.803271.
- Buron-Moles, Gemma, Anna Chailyan, Igor Dolejs, Jochen Forster, and Marta Hanna Mikš. 2019. 'Uncovering Carbohydrate Metabolism through a Genotype-Phenotype Association Study of 56 Lactic Acid Bacteria Genomes'. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 103(7):3135–52. doi:10.1007/s00253-019-09701-6.
- Chee, Wallace Jeng Yang, Shu Yih Chew, and Leslie Thian Lung Than. 2020. 'Vaginal Microbiota and the Potential of *Lactobacillus* Derivatives in Maintaining Vaginal Health'. *Microbial Cell Factories* 19(1):203. doi:10.1186/s12934-020-01464-4.
- Cho, Won-Il, and Myong-Soo Chung. 2020a. '*Bacillus* Spores: A Review of Their Properties and Inactivation Processing Technologies'. *Food Science and Biotechnology* 29(11):1447–61. doi:10.1007/s10068-020-00809-4.
- Coda, Rossana, Leena Melama, Carlo Giuseppe Rizzello, José Antonio Curiel, Juhani Sibakov, Ulla Holopainen, Marjo Pulkkinen, and Nesli Sozer. 2015. 'Effect of Air Classification and Fermentation by *Lactobacillus Plantarum* VTT E-133328 on Faba Bean (*Vicia Faba* L.) Flour Nutritional Properties'. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 193:34–42. doi:10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2014.10.012.
- Cui, Yanhua, Meihong Wang, Yankun Zheng, Kai Miao, and Xiaojun Qu. 2021. 'The Carbohydrate Metabolism of *Lactiplantibacillus Plantarum*'. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 22(24):13452. doi:10.3390/ijms222413452.
- Cui, Yi, Hongyun Wei, Fanggen Lu, Xiaowei Liu, Deliang Liu, Li Gu, and Chunhui Ouyang. 2016. 'Different Effects of Three Selected *Lactobacillus* Strains in Dextran Sulfate Sodium-Induced Colitis in BALB/c Mice' edited by F. Cominelli. *PLOS ONE* 11(2):e0148241. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0148241.
- Dash, Kshirod Kumar, Ufaq Fayaz, Aamir Hussain Dar, Rafeeya Shams, Sobiya Manzoor, Anjelina Sundarsingh, Pinky Deka, and Shafat Ahmad Khan. 2022. 'A Comprehensive Review on Heat Treatments and Related Impact on the Quality and Microbial Safety of Milk and Milk-Based Products'. *Food Chemistry Advances* 1:100041. doi:10.1016/j.focha.2022.100041.
- De Arauz, Luciana Juncioni, Angela Faustino Jozala, Priscila Gava Mazzola, and Thereza Christina Vessoni Penna. 2009. 'Nisin Biotechnological Production and Application: A Review'. *Trends in Food Science & Technology* 20(3–4):146–54. doi:10.1016/j.tifs.2009.01.056.
- De Giani, Alessandra, Federica Bovio, Matilde Forcella, Paola Fusi, Guido Sello, and Patrizia Di Gennaro. 2019. 'Identification of a Bacteriocin-like Compound from *Lactobacillus Plantarum* with Antimicrobial Activity and Effects on Normal and Cancerogenic Human Intestinal Cells'. *AMB Express* 9(1):88. doi:10.1186/s13568-019-0813-6.
- Deeth, Hilton C. 2006. 'Lipoprotein Lipase and Lipolysis in Milk'. *International Dairy Journal* 16(6):555–62. doi:10.1016/j.idairyj.2005.08.011.

- Doi, Yuki. 2019. 'Glycerol Metabolism and Its Regulation in Lactic Acid Bacteria'. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 103(13):5079–93. doi:10.1007/s00253-019-09830-y.
- Elshaghabee, Fouad M. F., Namita Rokana, Rohini D. Gulhane, Chetan Sharma, and Harsh Panwar. 2017. 'Bacillus As Potential Probiotics: Status, Concerns, and Future Perspectives'. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 8:1490. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2017.01490.
- Emmanuel Onyekachi Johnson, Goodluck Chigozie Okwuokei, Janet Ginikachi Okafor, Ibukun Akinboyewa, Ojinika Dabeluchukwu Ononye, Chidinma John, Nancy Okoro, Joseph Ochigbano, Prince Chiugo Chidi, and Nnanna Onwuka Orji. 2024. 'Antibacterial Activity of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Traditionally Fermented Food against Food Pathogen'. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews* 24(1):1962–73. doi:10.30574/wjarr.2024.24.1.3157.
- Errington, Jeffery, and Lizah T. Van Der Aart. 2020. 'Microbe Profile: *Bacillus Subtilis*: Model Organism for Cellular Development, and Industrial Workhorse: This Article Is Part of the Microbe Profiles Collection.' *Microbiology* 166(5):425–27. doi:10.1099/mic.0.000922.
- Farid, Muhammad Salman, Muhammad Imran Hussain, Sidra Rashid, Ramisha Ibtisam, Aniqqa Abbas, Sania Khalid, Piotr Salachna, and Łukasz Łopusiewicz. 2026. 'Applications of *Limosilactobacillus Fermentum* in Fruit and Vegetable Fermentations: Biotechnological Mechanisms, Nutritional Outcomes, and Industrial Relevance'. *Fermentation* 12(2):119. doi:10.3390/fermentation12020119.
- Filannino, Pasquale, Raffaella Di Cagno, and Marco Gobbetti. 2018. 'Metabolic and Functional Paths of Lactic Acid Bacteria in Plant Foods: Get out of the Labyrinth'. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology* 49:64–72. doi:10.1016/j.copbio.2017.07.016.
- Fischer, Sebastian W., and Fritz Titgemeyer. 2023. 'Protective Cultures in Food Products: From Science to Market'. *Foods* 12(7):1541. doi:10.3390/foods12071541.
- García, Apolinaria, Karen Navarro, Enrique Sanhueza, Susana Pineda, Edgar Pastene, Manuel Quezada, Karem Henríquez, Andrey Karlyshev, Julio Villena, and Carlos González. 2017. 'Characterization of *Lactobacillus Fermentum* UCO-979C, a Probiotic Strain with a Potent Anti-Helicobacter Pylori Activity'. *Electronic Journal of Biotechnology* 25:75–83. doi:10.1016/j.ejbt.2016.11.008.
- García-Cano, Israel, Diana Rocha-Mendoza, Joana Ortega-Anaya, Karen Wang, Erica Kosmerl, and Rafael Jiménez-Flores. 2019. 'Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Dairy Products as Potential Producers of Lipolytic, Proteolytic and Antibacterial Proteins'. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 103(13):5243–57. doi:10.1007/s00253-019-09844-6.
- Gauvry, Emilie, Anne-Gabrielle Mathot, Olivier Couvert, Ivan Leguérinel, and Louis Coroller. 2021. 'Effects of Temperature, pH and Water Activity on the Growth and the Sporulation Abilities of *Bacillus subtilis* BSB1'. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 337:108915. doi:10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2020.108915.
- Gedefa, Samuel, Debebe Lata, Seid Ebu, Genet Lakew, and Melaku Ankye. 2025. 'Lactic Acid Bacteria as Biological Food Preservatives: Genomic Insights and Applications'. *Science Frontiers* 6(4):159–69. doi:10.11648/j.sf.20250604.15.

- Gómez De Cadiñanos, Luz P., Tomás García-Cayuella, M. Carmen Martínez-Cuesta, Carmen Peláez, and Teresa Requena. 2019. 'Expression of Amino Acid Converting Enzymes and Production of Volatile Compounds by *Lactococcus lactis* IFPL953'. *International Dairy Journal* 96:29–35. doi:10.1016/j.idairyj.2019.04.004.
- Griffiths, M. W., and A. M. Tellez. 2013. 'Lactobacillus Helveticus: The Proteolytic System'. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 4. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2013.00030.
- Gupta, Debjyoti Sen, Sanjeev Gupta, and Jitendra Kumar, eds. 2021. *Breeding for Enhanced Nutrition and Bio-Active Compounds in Food Legumes*. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Hackl, Evelyn, Alexandra Ribarits, Nives Angerer, Markus Gansberger, Christine Hölzl, Cornelia Konlechner, Jutta Taferner-Kriegl, and Angela Sessitsch. 2013. 'Food of Plant Origin: Production Methods and Microbiological Hazards Linked to Food-borne Disease. Reference: CFT/EFSA/BIOHAZ/2012/01 Lot 2 (Food of Plant Origin with Low Water Content Such as Seeds, Nuts, Cereals, and Spices)'. *EFSA Supporting Publications* 10(4). doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2013.EN-403.
- He, Hehe, Qianqian Yu, Zhongyang Ding, Liang Zhang, Guiyang Shi, and Youran Li. 2023. 'Biotechnological and Food Synthetic Biology Potential of Platform Strain: *Bacillus licheniformis*'. *Synthetic and Systems Biotechnology* 8(2):281–91. doi:10.1016/j.synbio.2023.03.008.
- Hoover, Dallas G., and Susan K. Harlander. 1993. 'Screening Methods for Detecting Bacteriocin Activity'. Pp. 23–39 in *Bacteriocins of Lactic Acid Bacteria*. Elsevier.
- Hossain, Tanim Jabid. 2022. 'Functional Genomics of the Lactic Acid Bacterium *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* LAB-1: Metabolic, Probiotic and Biotechnological Perspectives'. *Heliyon* 8(11):e11412. doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11412.
- Jadán-Piedra, Carlos, Álvaro Crespo, Vicente Monedero, Dinoraz Vélez, Vicenta Devesa, and Manuel Zúñiga. 2019. 'Effect of Lactic Acid Bacteria on Mercury Toxicokinetics'. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 128:147–53. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2019.04.001.
- Ji, Qing-Yang, Wenqiong Wang, Haodong Yan, Hengxian Qu, Yang Liu, Yi Qian, and Ruixia Gu. 2023. 'The Effect of Different Organic Acids and Their Combination on the Cell Barrier and Biofilm of Escherichia Coli'. *Foods* 12(16):3011. doi:10.3390/foods12163011.
- Kang, Mi-Sun, Hae-Soon Lim, Jong-Suk Oh, You-jin Lim, Karin Wuertz-Kozak, Janette M. Harro, Mark E. Shirtliff, and Yvonne Achermann. 2017. 'Antimicrobial Activity of *Lactobacillus salivarius* and *Lactobacillus fermentum* against Staphylococcus Aureus'. *Pathogens and Disease* 75(2). doi:10.1093/femspd/ftx009.
- Kim, Minji, and Bokyung Son. 2025. 'Characterization of a Novel Bacteriophage PS1 Targeting *Bacillus licheniformis* for Biocontrol Application in Dairy Products'. *LWT* 222:117645. doi:10.1016/j.lwt.2025.117645.
- Kondrotiene, Kristina, Paulina Zavistanaviciute, Jurgita Aksomaitiene, Aleksandr Novoslavskij, and Mindaugas Malakauskas. 2023. '*Lactococcus lactis* in Dairy Fermentation—Health-

Promoting and Probiotic Properties'. *Fermentation* 10(1):16.
doi:10.3390/fermentation10010016.

König, Helmut, Gottfried Uden, and Jürgen Fröhlich, eds. 2017. *Biology of Microorganisms on Grapes, in Must and in Wine*. Cham: Springer International Publishing.

Kouviri, Matina, Demosthenes B. Panagiotakos, Christina Chrysohoou, Ekavi N. Georgousopoulou, Mary Yannakoulia, Dimitrios Tousoulis, Christos Pitsavos, Y. Skoumas, N. Katinioti, L. Papadimitriou, C. Masoura, S. Vellas, Y. Lentzas, M. Kambaxis, K. Paliou, V. Metaxa, N. Skourlis, C. Papanikolaou, A. Kalogeropoulou, E. Pitaraki, A. Laskaris, M. Hatzigeorgiou, A. Grekas, E. Kokkou, C. Vassiliadou, G. Dedousis, M. Toutouza-Giotsa, C. Tselika, S. Pouloupoulou, and M. Toutouza. 2020. 'Dairy Products, Surrogate Markers, and Cardiovascular Disease; a Sex-Specific Analysis from the ATTICA Prospective Study'. *Nutrition, Metabolism and Cardiovascular Diseases* 30(12):2194–2206. doi:10.1016/j.numecd.2020.07.037.

Kyrylenko, Alina, Robyn T. Eijlander, Giovanni Alliney, Elly Lucas-van De Bos, and Marjon H. J. Wells-Bennik. 2023a. 'Levels and Types of Microbial Contaminants in Different Plant-Based Ingredients Used in Dairy Alternatives'. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 407:110392. doi:10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2023.110392.

Kyrylenko, Alina, Robyn T. Eijlander, Giovanni Alliney, Elly Lucas-van De Bos, and Marjon H. J. Wells-Bennik. 2023b. 'Levels and Types of Microbial Contaminants in Different Plant-Based Ingredients Used in Dairy Alternatives'. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 407:110392. doi:10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2023.110392.

Landry, Erik J., Sam J. Fuchs, and Jinguo Hu. 2016. 'Carbohydrate Composition of Mature and Immature Faba Bean Seeds'. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis* 50:55–60. doi:10.1016/j.jfca.2016.05.010.

Larsen, N., M. G. Henriksen, C. Crocoll, Q. Li, R. Lametsch, M. M. Poojary, L. Krych, M. A. Petersen, and L. Jespersen. 2026. 'Enhancing the Sensory and Nutritional Properties of Faba Bean Protein through Fermentation with Lactic Acid Bacteria and *Bacillus* spp.'. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 446:111549. doi:10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2025.111549.

Lauková, Andrea, Martin Tomáška, Maria Joao Fraqueza, Renáta Szabóová, Eva Bino, Jana Ščerbová, Monika Pogány Simonová, and Emília Dvorožňáková. 2022. 'Bacteriocin-Producing Strain *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* LP17L/1 Isolated from Traditional Stored Ewe's Milk Cheese and Its Beneficial Potential'. *Foods* 11(7):959. doi:10.3390/foods11070959.

Lehri, B., A. M. Seddon, and A. V. Karlyshev. 2017. '*Lactobacillus fermentum* 3872 as a Potential Tool for Combatting *Campylobacter Jejuni* Infections'. *Virulence* 8(8):1753–60. doi:10.1080/21505594.2017.1362533.

Li, Tianlin, Tian Jiang, Ning Liu, Caiyun Wu, Huaide Xu, and Hongjie Lei. 2021. 'Biotransformation of Phenolic Profiles and Improvement of Antioxidant Capacities in Jujube Juice by Select Lactic Acid Bacteria'. *Food Chemistry* 339:127859. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.127859.

- Lu, Huiying J., Frederick Breidt, Ilenys M. Pérez-Díaz, and Jason A. Osborne. 2011. 'Antimicrobial Effects of Weak Acids on the Survival of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 under Anaerobic Conditions'. *Journal of Food Protection* 74(6):893–98. doi:10.4315/0362-028X.JFP-10-404.
- Luz, C., J. Ferrer, J. Mañes, and G. Meca. 2018. 'Toxicity Reduction of Ochratoxin A by Lactic Acid Bacteria'. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 112:60–66. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2017.12.030.
- Mafe, Alice Njolke, Great Iruoghene Edo, Raghda S. Makia, Ogunyemi Ayobami Joshua, Patrick Othuke Akpoghelie, Tayser Sumer Gaaz, Agatha Ngukuran Jikah, Emad Yousif, Endurance Fegor Isoje, Ufuoma Augustina Igbuku, Dina S. Ahmed, Arthur Efeoghene Athan Essaghah, and Huzaifa Umar. 2024. 'A Review on Food Spoilage Mechanisms, Food Borne Diseases and Commercial Aspects of Food Preservation and Processing'. *Food Chemistry Advances* 5:100852. doi:10.1016/j.focha.2024.100852.
- Mayer Labba, Inger-Cecilia, Hanne Frøkiær, and Ann-Sofie Sandberg. 2021. 'Nutritional and Antinutritional Composition of Fava Bean (*Vicia Faba* L., Var. Minor) Cultivars'. *Food Research International* 140:110038. doi:10.1016/j.foodres.2020.110038.
- Mazguene, Souhila. 2023. 'Lactic Acid Bacteria Metabolism: Mini-Review'. *Current Nutrition & Food Science* 19(2):94–104. doi:10.2174/1573401318666220527124256.
- Mínguez, M. Inés, and Diego Rubiales. 2021. 'Faba Bean'. Pp. 452–81 in *Crop Physiology Case Histories for Major Crops*. Elsevier.
- Mols, Maarten, and Tjakko Abee. 2011. '*Bacillus Cereus* Responses to Acid Stress'. *Environmental Microbiology* 13(11):2835–43. doi:10.1111/j.1462-2920.2011.02490.x.
- Pakdel, Mahsa, Sabihe Soleimani-Zad, and Safoura Akbari-Alavijeh. 2019. 'Screening of Lactic Acid Bacteria to Detect Potent Biosorbents of Lead and Cadmium'. *Food Control* 100:144–50. doi:10.1016/j.foodcont.2018.12.044.
- Papagianni, Maria. 2012. 'Metabolic Engineering of Lactic Acid Bacteria for the Production of Industrially Important Compounds'. *Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal* 3(4):e201210003. doi:10.5936/csbi.201210003.
- Param Pal Sahota, Bhavish Sood, and Mandeep Hunjan. 2017. 'Multidrug Resistant *Bacillus cereus* in Fresh Vegetables: A Serious Burden to Public Health'. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* 6(4):649–61. doi:10.20546/ijcmas.2017.604.080.
- Paramithiotis, Spiros. 2025. '*Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*, the Integral Member of Vegetable Fermentations'. *Applied Biosciences* 4(1):7. doi:10.3390/applbiosci4010007.
- Pérez-Ramos, Adrián, Désiré Madi-Moussa, Françoise Coucheney, and Djamel Drider. 2021. 'Current Knowledge of the Mode of Action and Immunity Mechanisms of LAB-Bacteriocins'. *Microorganisms* 9(10):2107. doi:10.3390/microorganisms9102107.
- Prete, Roberta, Sarah Louise Long, Alvaro Lopez Gallardo, Cormac G. Gahan, Aldo Corsetti, and Susan A. Joyce. 2020. 'Beneficial Bile Acid Metabolism from *Lactobacillus plantarum* of Food Origin'. *Scientific Reports* 10(1):1165. doi:10.1038/s41598-020-58069-5.

- Quinto, Emiliano J., Pilar Jiménez, Irma Caro, Jesús Tejero, Javier Mateo, and Tomás Girbés. 2014. 'Probiotic Lactic Acid Bacteria: A Review'. *Food and Nutrition Sciences* 05(18):1765–75. doi:10.4236/fns.2014.518190.
- Rahate, Kuldeep A., Mitali Madhumita, and Pramod K. Prabhakar. 2021. 'Nutritional Composition, Anti-Nutritional Factors, Pretreatments-Cum-Processing Impact and Food Formulation Potential of Faba Bean (*Vicia Faba* L.): A Comprehensive Review'. *LWT* 138:110796. doi:10.1016/j.lwt.2020.110796.
- Raman, Jegadeesh, Jun Su Noh, Jeong-Seon Kim, Gyeongjun Cho, Do-Hyun Kim, Jaekyung Song, and Soo-Jin Kim. 2025. 'Role of *Bacillus* Species in Food Industry: Advantages and Limitations'. *Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology* 35:e2507043. doi:10.4014/jmb.2507.07043.
- Revilla, Isabel. 2015. 'Impact of Thermal Processing on Faba Bean (*Vicia Faba*) Composition'. Pp. 337–43 in *Processing and Impact on Active Components in Food*. Elsevier.
- Rezvani, Fazlollah, Fatemeh Ardestani, and Ghasem Najafpour. 2017. 'Growth Kinetic Models of Five Species of *Lactobacilli* and Lactose Consumption in Batch Submerged Culture'. *Brazilian Journal of Microbiology* 48(2):251–58. doi:10.1016/j.bjm.2016.12.007.
- Riaz Rajoka, Muhammad Shahid, Hafiza Mahreen Mehwish, Muhammad Siddiq, Zhao Haobin, Jing Zhu, Li Yan, Dongyan Shao, Xiaoguang Xu, and Junling Shi. 2017. 'Identification, Characterization, and Probiotic Potential of *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* Isolated from Human Milk'. *LWT* 84:271–80. doi:10.1016/j.lwt.2017.05.055.
- Riaz, Saba, Syed Kashif Nawaz, and Shahida Hasnain. 2010. 'Bacteriocins Produced by *L. fermentum* and *L. acidophilus* Can Inhibit Cephalosporin Resistant E .Coli.' *Brazilian Journal of Microbiology* 41(3):643–48. doi:10.1590/S1517-83822010000300015.
- Ricke, Sc. 2003. 'Perspectives on the Use of Organic Acids and Short Chain Fatty Acids as Antimicrobials'. *Poultry Science* 82(4):632–39. doi:10.1093/ps/82.4.632.
- Rodriguez, J. H., M. A. Cousin, and P. E. Nelson. 1993. 'Thermal Resistance and Growth of *Bacillus licheniformis* and *Bacillus subtilis* in Tomato Juice'. *Journal of Food Protection* 56(2):165–68. doi:10.4315/0362-028X-56.2.165.
- Rossoni, Rodnei Dennis, Patrícia Pimentel De Barros, Janaina Araújo De Alvarenga, Felipe De Camargo Ribeiro, Marisol Dos Santos Velloso, Beth Burgwyn Fuchs, Eleftherios Mylonakis, Antonio Olavo Cardoso Jorge, and Juliana Campos Junqueira. 2018. 'Antifungal Activity of Clinical *Lactobacillus* Strains against *Candida Albicans* Biofilms: Identification of Potential Probiotic Candidates to Prevent Oral Candidiasis'. *Biofouling* 34(2):212–25. doi:10.1080/08927014.2018.1425402.
- Ruiz Rodríguez, Luciana G., Florencia Mohamed, Juliana Bleckwedel, Roxana Medina, Luc De Vuyst, Elvira M. Hebert, and Fernanda Mozzi. 2019. 'Diversity and Functional Properties of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated From Wild Fruits and Flowers Present in Northern Argentina'. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 10:1091. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2019.01091.

- Setlow, Peter. 2014. 'Germination of Spores of *Bacillus* Species: What We Know and Do Not Know'. *Journal of Bacteriology* 196(7):1297–1305. doi:10.1128/JB.01455-13.
- Siedler, Solvej, Rafik Balti, and Ana Rute Neves. 2019. 'Bioprotective Mechanisms of Lactic Acid Bacteria against Fungal Spoilage of Food'. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology* 56:138–46. doi:10.1016/j.copbio.2018.11.015.
- Singh, D., A. Kumar, A. K. Singh, C. R. Prajapati, and H. S. Tripathi. 2013. 'Studies on Survivability of Field Pea Rust Caused by *Uromyces Viciae-Fabae* (Pers.) de Bary in Tarai Region of Uttarakhand (India)'. *African Journal of Agricultural Research* 8(17):1617–22. doi:10.5897/AJAR12.1003.
- Soltani, Samira, Eric Biron, Laila Ben Said, Muriel Subirade, and Ismail Fliss. 2022. 'Bacteriocin-Based Synergetic Consortia: A Promising Strategy to Enhance Antimicrobial Activity and Broaden the Spectrum of Inhibition' edited by K. L. Hockett. *Microbiology Spectrum* 10(1):e00406-21. doi:10.1128/spectrum.00406-21.
- Song, Adelene Ai-Lian, Lionel L. A. In, Swee Hua Erin Lim, and Raha Abdul Rahim. 2017a. 'A Review on *Lactococcus lactis*: From Food to Factory'. *Microbial Cell Factories* 16(1):55. doi:10.1186/s12934-017-0669-x.
- Soni, Aswathi, Indrawati Oey, Pat Silcock, and Phil Bremer. 2016. '*Bacillus* Spores in the Food Industry: A Review on Resistance and Response to Novel Inactivation Technologies'. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety* 15(6):1139–48. doi:10.1111/1541-4337.12231.
- Sorathiya, Kavita Bhavin, Adma Melo, Maria Conceição Hogg, and Manuela Pintado. 2025. 'Organic Acids in Food Preservation: Exploring Synergies, Molecular Insights, and Sustainable Applications'. *Sustainability* 17(8):3434. doi:10.3390/su17083434.
- Sun, Rongxue, An Vermeulen, and Frank Devlieghere. 2021. 'Modeling the Combined Effect of Temperature, pH, Acetic and Lactic Acid Concentrations on the Growth/No Growth Interface of Acid-Tolerant *Bacillus* Spores'. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 360:109419. doi:10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2021.109419.
- Thani, Arthit, Lakkana Laopaiboon, Sukanda Vichitphan, Vichean Leelavatcharamas, and Pattana Laopaiboon. n.d. 'Lactic Acid Production by *Lactococcus lactis* in Batch Cultures Using Single and Mixed Sugars'.
- V. Dzhavakhiya, Vakhtang, Elena V. Glagoleva, Veronika V. Savelyeva, Natalia V. Statsyuk, Maksim I. Kartashov, Tatiana M. Voinova, Alla V. Sergeeva, 1 Laboratory of Biotechnology of Physiologically Active Compounds, Federal Research Centre "Fundamentals of Biotechnology", Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow 117312, Russia, 2 Department of Molecular Biology, All-Russian Research Institute of Phytopathology, Bolshie Vyazemy, Moscow region 143050, Russia, and 3 FermLab LLC, Moscow 123592, Russia. 2018. 'New Bacitracin-Resistant Nisin-Producing Strain of *Lactococcus lactis* and Its Physiological Characterization'. *AIMS Microbiology* 4(4):608–21. doi:10.3934/microbiol.2018.4.608.
- Valente, Inês M., Margarida R. G. Maia, Nertila Malushi, Hugo M. Oliveira, Lumturi Papa, José A. Rodrigues, António J. M. Fonseca, and Ana R. J. Cabrita. 2018. 'Profiling of Phenolic

Compounds and Antioxidant Properties of European Varieties and Cultivars of *Vicia Faba* L. Pods'. *Phytochemistry* 152:223–29. doi:10.1016/j.phytochem.2018.05.011.

- Verni, Michela, Changyin Wang, Marco Montemurro, Maria De Angelis, Kati Katina, Carlo G. Rizzello, and Rossana Coda. 2017. 'Exploring the Microbiota of Faba Bean: Functional Characterization of Lactic Acid Bacteria'. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 8:2461. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2017.02461.
- Wang, Li, Matthijs Dekker, Jenneke Heising, Liming Zhao, and Vincenzo Fogliano. 2024. 'Food Matrix Design Can Influence the Antimicrobial Activity in the Food Systems: A Narrative Review'. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition* 64(25):8963–89. doi:10.1080/10408398.2023.2205937.
- Wei, Chaozhi, Leilei Yu, Nanzhen Qiao, Shumin Wang, Fengwei Tian, Jianxin Zhao, Hao Zhang, Qixiao Zhai, and Wei Chen. 2020. 'The Characteristics of Patulin Detoxification by *Lactobacillus plantarum* 13M5'. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 146:111787. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2020.111787.
- Wei, Ziqi, Pengrong Fan, Bo Li, Philippe Madjirebaye, Zhen Peng, and Tao Xiong. 2025. 'Optimization of Culture Medium Ingredients and Culture Conditions for Bacteriocin Production in *Lactococcus lactis* NCU036019'. *Biotechnology and Applied Biochemistry* 72(4):985–98. doi:10.1002/bab.2714.
- Wilks, Jessica C., Ryan D. Kitko, Sarah H. Cleeton, Grace E. Lee, Chinagozi S. Ugwu, Brian D. Jones, Sandra S. BonDurant, and Joan L. Slonczewski. 2009. 'Acid and Base Stress and Transcriptomic Responses in *Bacillus Subtilis*'. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 75(4):981–90. doi:10.1128/AEM.01652-08.
- Wu, Caiyun, Tianlin Li, Jing Qi, Tian Jiang, Huaide Xu, and Hongjie Lei. 2020. 'Effects of Lactic Acid Fermentation-Based Biotransformation on Phenolic Profiles, Antioxidant Capacity and Flavor Volatiles of Apple Juice'. *LWT* 122:109064. doi:10.1016/j.lwt.2020.109064.
- Yang, En, Lihua Fan, Jinping Yan, Yueming Jiang, Craig Doucette, Sherry Fillmore, and Bradley Walker. 2018. 'Influence of Culture Media, pH and Temperature on Growth and Bacteriocin Production of Bacteriocinogenic Lactic Acid Bacteria'. *AMB Express* 8(1):10. doi:10.1186/s13568-018-0536-0.
- Yang, Haoran, Yongjian Yu, Caixia Fu, and Fusheng Chen. 2019. 'Bacterial Acid Resistance Toward Organic Weak Acid Revealed by RNA-Seq Transcriptomic Analysis in *Acetobacter Pasteurianus*'. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 10:1616. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2019.01616.
- Zhao, Yan, Kan Hong, Jianxin Zhao, Hao Zhang, Qixiao Zhai, and Wei Chen. 2019. '*Lactobacillus fermentum* and Its Potential Immunomodulatory Properties'. *Journal of Functional Foods* 56:21–32. doi:10.1016/j.jff.2019.02.044.
- Zhou, Rong, Benita Hyldgaard, Xiaqing Yu, Eva Rosenqvist, Rosina Magaña Ugarte, Shanxiang Yu, Zhen Wu, Carl-Otto Ottosen, and Tongmin Zhao. 2018. 'Phenotyping of Faba Beans (*Vicia Faba* L.) under Cold and Heat Stresses Using Chlorophyll Fluorescence'. *Euphytica* 214(4):68. doi:10.1007/s10681-018-2154-y.

Zotta, T., E. Parente, and A. Ricciardi. 2017. 'Aerobic Metabolism in the Genus *Lactobacillus* : Impact on Stress Response and Potential Applications in the Food Industry'. *Journal of Applied Microbiology* 122(4):857–69. doi:10.1111/jam.13399.

7 Appendix

Appendix 1 – Plate pictures from lawn assay

24 h of LAB incubation

48 h of LAB incubation

29-05-2026 16

29-05-2026

Appendix 2 – Plate pictures from supernatant inhibition

Table 3. pH values of LAB cell-free supernatants before inhibition treatment.

LAB strains	pH
Lp. UFLA SAY 96	3.82
Lp. 36h8h1	3.93
Lf. ZN1-10	4.76
Lf. 6h2.cm1	4.47
LL. MT III-6.1.4	4.29

Table 4. Viable counts of *Bacillus* strains after 48 h treatment with LAB supernatants. Viable counts of *Bacillus subtilis* fb1, *Bacillus licheniformis* fb2, and *Bacillus subtilis* natto were determined by plate counting after 48 h exposure to different ratios of LAB supernatants. Values are expressed as CFU/mL. ND, not detected; TMTC, too many to count, indicating counts higher than the countable range and at least $>10^5$ CFU/mL.

LAB strain	Supernatant ratio	Bs.fb1	Bl.fb2	Bs.Natto
Lf. ZN1-10	25%	2.00E+08	1.20E+08	3.10E+07
	50%	1.60E+07	3.90E+02	ND
	75%	8.00E+01	0.00E+00	6.20E+02
Lf. 6h2.cm1	25%	1.00E+08	ND	4.00E+07
	50%	3.60E+02	ND	1.20E+02
	75%	7.10E+02	ND	0.00E+00
LL. MTIII-6.1.4	25%	3.60E+08	2.40E+08	1.50E+08
	50%	3.00E+08	2.50E+08	1.16E+08
	75%	TMTC	TMTC	TMTC

Appendix 3 – Plate pictures from pH tolerance of *Bacillus* spp.

Bacillus subtilis fb1

Bacillus licheformis fb2

Bacillus subtilis natto

Bacillus subtilis fb1

Bacillus licheformis fb2

Bacillus subtilis natto

Bs.fb1

Bl.fb2

Bs.natto

Appendix 4 – Plate pictures from well diffusion assay

Appendix 5 – Plate pictures from the organic acids inhibition of *Bacillus* spp.

Table 5 pH values of BHI medium adjusted with different concentrations of lactic acid and acetic acid.

Concentration	Lactic acid	Acetic acid
20 mM	5.66	5.67
40 mM	4.57	4.78
60 mM	4.21	4.67
80 mM	3.97	4.51

Lactic acid - Bs.fb1

Lactic acid - Bl.fb2

Lactic acid - Bs.natto

Acetic acid - Bs.fb1

Acetic acid - Bl.fb2

Acetic acid - Bs.natto

Appendix 6 – Pictures of fermentation samples

Appendix 7 – Calibration curves used in fermentation

Figure 16. Calibration curve between OD₆₀₀ nm and viable cell counts of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*. Viable cell counts were expressed as CFU/mL.

Figure 17. Calibration curve between OD₆₀₀ nm and viable cell counts of *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*. Viable cell counts were expressed as CFU/mL.

Figure 18. Calibration curve between OD₆₀₀ nm and viable cell counts of *Lactococcus lactis*. Viable cell counts were expressed as CFU/mL.

Figure 19. HPLC standard calibration curve of lactic acid showing the relationship between peak area and lactic acid concentration (g/L).

Figure 20. HPLC standard calibration curve of acetic acid showing the relationship between peak area and acetic acid concentration (g/L).

Declaration of using generative AI tools (for students)

I/we have used generative AI as an aid/tool

I/we have NOT used generative AI as an aid/tool

List which GAI tools you have used and include the link to the platform (if possible):

Chatgpt
<https://chatgpt.com>

Describe how generative AI has been used in the exam paper:

Purpose:

- 1) Coding for data analysis
- 2) Grammar checking and improvement

Please note: Content generated by GAI that is used as a source in the paper requires correct use of quotation marks and source referencing. Read the guidelines from Copenhagen University Library at KUnet.